

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS
No. 80 – September 2025 · <https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/>

An extensive bloom of filamentous cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea region in summer 2025

An extensive cyanobacteria bloom was observed in the Baltic Sea region in summer 2025. During the same period, cyanotoxins were detected in bivalve shellfish harvested along the Swedish Skagerrak coast. The temporal overlap between the bloom and the toxin detection, with a short delay, suggests that the cyanotoxins in bivalve shellfish may have originated from the Baltic Sea bloom and were likely transported by surface currents into the mussel farming locations within the Skagerrak. Potentially, the cyanobacteria had been growing in the unusually warm waters in the Kattegat. Here we report on this large bloom and ongoing efforts to develop an early warning system for harmful algal blooms (HABs).

The Baltic Sea is a brackish shelf sea connected to the North Sea through narrow straits leading to the Kattegat, a transitional area connecting it to the Skagerrak. The Baltic Sea is divided into

different sub-basins, mainly the Baltic Proper, which has surface salinities in the range ~6–10, while the Bothnian Sea and the northernmost Bothnian Bay have salinities of approximately 5 and <3, respectively. Surface temperatures in summer sometimes reach 20°C offshore and may be higher in protected bays and archipelagos. HABs are common in the area and affect tourism and the marine ecosystem [1]. Nitrogen-fixing, filamentous cyanobacteria from the order Nostocales form surface blooms in summer [2–3]. The dominant taxa contributing most of the biomass are *Aphanizomenon flos-aquae*, *Nodularia spumigena*, and *Dolichospermum* spp. [2, 4]. These cyanobacteria play a key role in the Baltic Sea food web [5–6]. When sinking to the seafloor, their biomass is degraded in a process that consumes oxygen, which can lead to low-oxygen conditions in the deeper parts of the Baltic Sea. The hepatotoxin nodu-

Fig. 1. Satellite image showing the distribution of near-surface cyanobacteria bloom on 20 July 2025 in Lausvik Bay, southeastern Gotland, a large island in the Baltic Proper. ESA-Sentinel 2 processed by SMHI. Quasi true colour RGB.

unesco

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

Content

Feature article

An extensive bloom of filamentous cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea region in summer 2025
Bengt Karlson and colleagues 1

HAB events and prediction

Updated high-resolution index for *Karenia brevis* impacts in Florida..... 5

Digital Holography for HAB Monitoring in Lake Erie..... 10

Lingulaulax polyedra bloom in Romania 12

Benthic *Prorocentrum* in five countries of Oceania 15

Checklist of HAB species in Santa Marta, Colombia 18

HAB Training and networking

Symposium on Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific 21

BlueShellfish MCSA Staff Exchange in Italy 23

New projects and opportunities

Phycotoxins in the Arctic (PHATE) 25

Interview with *Barrie Dale* 27

Red Tides Archives

Youssef Halim, the Creator of a “Celebrity”: *Alexandrium* 34

Rut Akselman in Memoriam 37

Beyond HAB Science

Takayama carved models of Microalgae 39

Forthcoming

ICHA 2025 in October, Chile 41

Mixoplankton session in AGU/ASLO, February 2026 42

Dino13 in Bremen, July 2026 42

Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS) in Exeter, September 2026 43

larin is produced by *N. spumigena* and has previously been detected in, for example, European flounder (*Platichthys flesus*), blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) and common eider ducks (*Somateria mollissima*) in the Baltic Sea [7–8].

A multi-method approach was applied to study the bloom dynamics, including phytoplankton distribution, composition, and biomass. Satellite remote sensing of ocean colour, through the Baltic Algae Watch System, operated by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), provided daily updates on the distribution of near-surface cyanobacterial accumulations. Thresholds of reflectance at specific wavelengths were applied to distinguish between bloom or no-bloom conditions [2–3]. To minimize the impact of cloud cover, composite images were generated using observations collected during seven-day periods. *In situ* fluorometers configured with excitation and emission wavelengths specific for phycocyanin [9] – a pigment indicative of filamentous cyanobacteria – were employed to assess the distribution of the cyanobacteria. The fluorometers were mounted on an ocean glider, integrated into depth-profiling instruments, and included in an underway system on R/V Svea. These bio-optical instruments yielded data on both the horizontal and vertical distribution of the cyanobacteria in the water. In addition, the Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) [10–12], an imaging flow cytometer integrated in the flow-through system on the research vessel, and manual microscopy of water samples collected at sampling stations, provided detailed information on species composition, abundance and biomass.

The month of June 2025 was characterized by windy conditions, and cyanobacterial surface accumulations were first observed from satellite in early July. However, preliminary analyses of *in situ* phycocyanin fluorescence data from an ocean glider off the west coast of Gotland indicate that the bloom was already ongoing earlier (data not shown). It is likely that wind-driven mixing prevented the formation of surface blooms in June, but that cyanobacteria were proliferating deeper in the water column. In July, near-surface accumulations of cyanobacteria were observed using satellites (see example

Fig. 2. Air temperature (A) and wind speed (B) on Gotland, summer 2025. Three-day running means with hourly data in the background. Data from station Hoburg A, SMHI.

Fig. 3. Map showing the observations of near surface accumulations of cyanobacteria between 14 and 20 July 2025. Colours indicate the number of days when surface accumulations were observed during the seven-day period. Source: SMHI Baltic Algae Watch System. <https://www.smhi.se/data/hav-och-havsmiljo/alger/data-fran-algovervakning>

Biomass, mg C L⁻¹

- 5 × 10⁻¹
- 1 × 10⁻²
- 1.5 × 10⁻²
- 2 × 10⁻²

Fig. 4. Map showing the biomass of two cyanobacteria species in summer 2025. (A). *N. spumigena* 14–20 July. (B). *N. spumigena* 9–16 August. (C). *A. flos-aquae* 14–20 July. (D). *A. flos-aquae* 9–16 August. Results are based on automated plankton analyses using the IFCB operated as part of the flow-through system on R/V Svea. Black points indicate stations where samples were collected but the taxon was not detected.

Fig. 5. *Nodularia spumigena* and *Aphanizomenon flos-aquae*: examples of images from the IFCB.

in Fig. 1). A period of high air temperatures and low wind speed (Fig. 2) coincided with daily satellite observations of cyanobacterial blooms, with their maximum extent reached in late July (Fig. 3). The bloom covered most of the Baltic Proper, the Gulf of Finland, and the Bothnian Sea. Blooms in the Bothnian Sea have become more common in recent years [2]. Results from the IFCB, operated during a R/V Svea cruise (14–20 July), show the distribution and biomass of cyanobacteria (Fig. 4). *N. spumigena* and *A. flos-aquae* (Fig. 5) were observed in high amounts along the ship's route in the Baltic Proper, but in much lower amounts in the Kattegat and Skagerrak (Figs. 4A, 4C). During another cruise with the same vessel (9–16 August), the bloom had declined in the Baltic Proper but *N. spumigena* and *A. flos-aquae* were observed in higher amounts in the Kattegat (Figs. 4B, 4D) using IFCB. Results from microscopy (not shown) confirmed the IFCB data. During the same period, several species of bivalve shellfish harvested along the Swedish Skagerrak coast were found to contain varying concentrations of nodularin. Presence of this toxin in bivalves from the same region was reported earlier [13]. As there is currently no established regulatory limit for nodularin in mussel meat, the authorities advised a cautionary principle against all recreational harvesting in both the affected and adjacent coastal areas.

The results presented here show that a major cyanobacterial bloom occurred in the Baltic Sea in summer 2025 and that the bloom extended into the more saline waters of the Kattegat and the Skagerrak. Cyanobacteria observed at these higher salinities appeared healthy when observed in the microscope, suggesting that local populations may contribute to blooms under favourable conditions. Blooms of cyanobacteria in the Kattegat are rare: the last major event was in 2006, when a large bloom was also observed in the Southern Baltic Proper. Salinity has been thought to constrain the growth of *N. spumigena* in the Kattegat, where surface salinities are ~15–20. However, *N. spumigena* has recently been reported in the Great Salt Lake (USA) at salinities up to 45 [14].

Finding cyanotoxins in bivalves indicates a potential risk for human health.

Fig. 6. The map illustrates the advection of neutrally buoyant particles in the surface layer (0–2 m) from 18 July to 1 August 2025. The NEMO-Nordic ocean model was used to backtrack 400 particles distributed within the rectangle in the Kattegat and southern Skagerrak. The colours of lines indicate the modelled paths of individual particles. Particle simulations forced by NEMO-Nordic operational ocean model from the Baltic Marine Forecasting Centre (BAL MFC), run by SMHI and available via Copernicus Marine Services (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00010>).

Cyanotoxins have previously been observed in harvested molluscs in the Baltic Sea [15], indicating the same risk in this area. Swedish marine monitoring, along with two ongoing research projects, contributed to the results presented here. The aims are to learn more about cyanobacteria and their toxins and to develop an early warning system combining observations and short-term modelling [16], based on SMHI's operational ocean modelling [17], see example in Fig. 6. Tourism and desalination facilities on Gotland are two sectors that may benefit from these results.

Acknowledgements

Funding for the work presented was received through two projects: Swedish Research Council Formas 2022-02117 *A new forecast framework for algae bloom hazard to secure future water supply and development of tourism on Gotland* and the Swedish Board of Agriculture 2022-4385 *Establishment of the*

Center for Environmental Monitoring of Algal Toxins – from sampling to communication with the public. The latter project was co-funded by the European Union through the Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Programme (EMFAF) 2021-2027. We are grateful to Anna Willstrand Wranne and colleagues at the Voice of the Ocean Foundation for providing and operating the ocean glider SW of island Gotland. The captain, crew and SMHI-personnel on R/V Svea are thanked for collecting samples and operating the Imaging Flow Cytobot as part of the ship's underway Ferrybox system.

References

1. Karlson B et al 2021. *Harmful Algae* 102:101989. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2021.101989
2. Karlson B et al 2022. *Harmful Algae* 118:102291. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2022.102291
3. Kahru M & Elmgren R 2014. *Biogeosciences* 11(13):3619. doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-3619-2014

4. Olofsson M et al 2020. *Harmful Algae* 91:101685. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101685
5. Suikkanen S et al 2010. *Deep-Sea Res Part II-Top Stud Oceanogr* 57(3–4):199–209. doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2009.09.014
6. Suikkanen S 2021. *Food Webs* e00202. doi.org/10.1016/j.fooweb.2021.e00202
7. Sipiä VO et al 2001. *Environ Toxicol* 16(2):121–126. doi.org/10.1002/tox.1015
8. Sipiä VO et al 2006. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 25(11):2834–2839. doi.org/10.1897/06-185r.1
9. Seppälä J et al 2007. *Estuar Coast Shelf Sci* 73(3–4):489–500. doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2007.02.015
10. Kraft K et al 2025. *Harmful Algae* 147:102865. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102865
11. Olson RJ & Sosik HM 2007. *Limnol Oceanogr-Methods* 5:195–203. doi.org/10.4319/lom.2007.5.195
12. Sosik HM & Olson RJ 2007. *Limnol Oceanogr-Methods* 5:204–216. doi.org/10.4319/lom.2007.5.204
13. España A et al 2023. *Toxins* 15(5):329. doi.org/10.3390/toxins15050329
14. Wurtsbaugh WA et al 2025. *Harmful Algae*:102959. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102959
15. Olofsson M et al. 2025. *Harmful Algae* 147:102885. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102885
16. Karlson B 2023. *Early detection and early warning of harmful cyanobacteria blooms*, In: Joint FAO-IOC-IAEA technical guidance for the implementation of early warning systems for harmful algal blooms., Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper, FAO, IOC, IAEA (Eds.), Rome. pp. 186–200. doi.org/10.4060/cc4794en
17. Kärnä T et al 2021. *Geosci Model Dev* 14:5731–5749. doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-5731-2021.

Authors

Bengt Karlson, Lars Arneborg, Lars Axell, Mikael Hedblom, Maria Karlberg & Anders Torstensson, Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Oceanography, Sweden

Inga Koszalka, Department of Meteorology, Stockholm University, Sweden

Malin Olofsson, Department of Aquatic Sciences and Assessment, Sweden

Malin Persson & Aida Zuberovic Muratovic, Swedish Food Agency, Sweden

Email corresponding author: bengt.karlson@smhi.se

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220194>

An updated high-resolution, site-specific *Karenia brevis* bloom severity index and associated respiratory irritation impacting the southwest Florida coast

Fig. 1. Study area and location in Florida (inset), showing Florida Wildlife Research Institute (FWRI) cell sample locations (red circles). The yellow squares indicate the eight Beach Conditions Reporting System (BCRS) beach sites in Manatee and Sarasota Counties that are monitored by the Mote Marine Lab.

Recurring “red tides” along the coast of southwest Florida, caused by the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis*, typically begin in late summer or fall. They can persist for months to over a year, and extend from tens to hundreds of kilometers along the shoreline [1–2]. These blooms are problematic because *K. brevis* produces brevetoxins (BTX)—potent neurotoxins that accumulate in shellfish. The resulting risk of neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) triggers widespread closures of shellfish beds to

protect consumers. Additionally, when *K. brevis* cells rupture, BTXs become aerosolized through wave breaking or wind-driven turbulence [3–4]. Exposure to aerosolized BTXs causes respiratory irritation or illness in beachgoers and increased emergency room visits [5]. As a result, both residents and tourists often avoid beaches when red tides are reported [6], causing significant economic losses to local businesses [7]. Severe blooms can also cause fish kills and mass mortalities of endangered

manatees, bottlenose dolphins, sea turtles, and seabirds [8].

Although the public often perceives blooms as affecting the entire west coast of Florida, they are typically patchy and shift with oceanic currents. Capturing these spatial and temporal variations is essential for developing accurate location-specific bloom severity indices. In 2022, our group developed the first fine-scale indices for *K. brevis* bloom intensity and associated respiratory irritation for southwest Florida [9]. The Bloom Severity Index (BSI) was based on *K. brevis* cell concentrations collected by the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC) from 1953–2019. The concentrations were binned by month into 0.2° latitudinal sections along the shoreline, and the frequency with which threshold concentrations were exceeded in each bin across the region was calculated for each month or each year to give a severity estimate [9]. A normalized BSI was defined from 0–10, with 10 representing the most severe bloom and 0 representing absence. Because the BSI reflects both spatial and temporal extent, it is a valuable dataset for assessing site-specific severity and validating future bloom models [9].

To quantify respiratory impacts, a corresponding Respiratory Irritation Index (RI) was developed for 2006–2019 using Beach Condition Reporting System (BCRS) data from Mote Marine Laboratory. Volunteers routinely reported respiratory irritation at six Sarasota County beach sites (2006–2025) and two in Manatee County (since 2007) (Fig. 1). Reports include time, location, and respiratory irritation severity measure determined by the frequency of coughs and sneezes heard over 30-second intervals. The resulting respiratory measures were categorized as producing no, slight, moderate, or high (severe) respiratory irritation. The monthly and annual RIs were then quantified as percentage of beach days during each month where respiratory problems were reported. Similar to the BSI, a normalized 10-point RI scale was

Fig. 2. (A) Hovmöller (time-latitude) diagram for the 0.15-degree latitude-binned monthly-maxima of observed *K. brevis* cell counts within 5 km (3 mile) polygon (as shown in Fig. 1) from 1953 to early 2024. (B) The Bloom Severity Index (BSI) for southwest Florida [25.4°–28.4° N], represent the relative number of “bin-months” normalized to a maximum value of ten. For each bin, the maximal cell count was determined and classified into five categories: <5,000 (light gray), >5,000 >50,000 >100,000 and >1,000,000 cells L⁻¹ (salmon color to dark red). White in (A) indicates no samples were taken. In (B), black crosses on the x-axis indicate months with no cell observations in the entire region, and gray circles indicate months where samples were available but no blooms were observed. See [9] for binning methods.

Fig. 3. Annual Bloom Severity Index (BSI, July to next June) for (A) the Southwest Florida coast ranging from Collier to Pinellas Counties (see Figure 1), (B) Pinellas County, (C) Manatee and Sarasota Counties, (D) Lee and Charlotte Counties and (E) Collier County. Some counties were combined because of their shorter shorelines compared to others. The BSI for each county was derived using the same approach as in (A), except that they were normalized by the total number of 0.15-degree latitudinal bins for that county. Black crosses indicate no samples taken, and gray circles indicate samples with no blooms observed.

developed, with 10 representing the highest number of beach days and 0 representing the lowest.

Over the past two decades, the quantity and frequency of sampling of *K. brevis* densities along the southwest Florida shoreline has progressively increased, owing to significant efforts coordinated by the FWC. To take advantage of this higher-resolution dataset, we reanalyzed the historical data by partitioning it into smaller 0.15° latitude bins by month and adding the five recent years of data [9]. The dataset now spans from 1953 through 2024, ending with the 2023 bloom year (defined as July–June of the following year,

since blooms typically begin in the latter half of the year). This analysis only included data collected within ~4.8 km of the coast (Fig. 1), where cell counts are most consistently available. As before, each monthly bin was examined to determine whether the maximum cell count exceeded any of five categories (Fig. 2A; see caption for details), and severity indices were calculated. The five categories were defined as follows. Below 5,000 cells L⁻¹ is considered safe and >5,000 cells L⁻¹ is the threshold above which shellfish beds may be closed. The other thresholds, low, medium and high, are based on potential risk categories used by FWC. The low

category, >50,000 cells L⁻¹, indicates when individuals most sensitive to respiratory irritation begin to experience symptoms [9]. The medium category, >100,000 cells L⁻¹, designates when all beachgoers have an increased likelihood of experiencing respiratory irritation. A high concentration, >1,000,000 cells L⁻¹, represent a probable risk of discomfort and adverse health effects. Revised severity indices were calculated using the binned data for these five categories. To assess respiratory impacts, we also extended the RI from our previous work [9] to January 2025 based on the updated BCRS data.

Bloom Severity Index (BSI). Compar-

Fig. 4. (A). The monthly Respiratory Irritation (RI) index for the eight Beach Condition Reporting System (BCRS) stations in Sarasota and Manatee Counties, FL, was derived from data collected from August 2006 to January 2025. Black crosses represent months with no available BCRS data reported, and gray circles indicate months with no reported respiratory irritation. (B). The accumulated RI was calculated for each bloom year (from August to July of the following year). The 2024 RI index includes data only from August 2024 to January 2025. (C). The Annual BSI for Sarasota and Manatee Counties. In all panels, black crosses indicate months with no cell observations or respiratory irritation reports available for the two counties, while gray circles indicate months where samples were available but no blooms were observed.

Table 1. The percent of the time when *Karenia brevis* cell concentrations >5,000, >50,000, or >100,000 cells L⁻¹ were observed in a given 0.15° latitude bin, that increasingly higher cell concentrations would also be present at the same location during the same monthly time period.

<i>K. brevis</i> cells L ⁻¹	>5,000	>50,000	>100,000	>1,000,000
>5,000	-	71%	61%	24%
>50,000	-	-	86%	34%
>100,000	-	-	-	39%

ing the updated Hovmöller diagram with our previous version shows that the current 0.15° bin resolution dataset (previously 0.20° latitudinal bins), provides finer spatial detail along the coast with fewer gaps (Fig. 2A–B). The normalized monthly BSI along southwest Florida shoreline was almost identical to Stumpf et al. (2022) [9], though minor differences exist (Fig. 2A). Notably, the March 2023 bloom in this updated index replaced the previously February 2016 [8], as the highest BSI score of 10, reflecting the most extensive bloom of >5,000 cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 2B). The months with the widest extent of more intense bloom concentrations can also be identified; for instance, August 2018 exhibited the broadest bloom at concentrations > 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ (BSI = 7.1). (Note that the 2023 dataset is provisional and may undergo minor revisions after quality control.)

Interannual variability of K. brevis blooms in southwest Florida and individual counties. For the area from Pinellas to Collier counties, the highest BSI at 5,000 cells L⁻¹ occurred in bloom year 2002 (Fig. 3A) (Pasco and Hernando counties were excluded in this analysis due to inconsistent sampling; Fig. 2A). During 2002, although the bloom was continuous in space and time (Fig. 2A), it was not sufficiently intense to rank among the most severe bloom years. Examination of the bloom concentrations >100,000 cells L⁻¹ threshold showed that years such as 2001, 2006, 2012, 2018, and 2022 recorded higher BSIs. The 2020 bloom persisted into 2021, producing an intense summer bloom that year. Similarly, the 2017 bloom extended into 2018, culminating in a severe bloom in the summer of 2018 with a maximum BSI at >10⁶ cells L⁻¹ in July. Over the past three decades, two bloom years stand out for their absence of blooms: 2010, when *K. brevis*

was not detected along the southwest Florida coast, and 2023, when only a few samples recorded low cell counts. This stands in stark contrast to the comparatively severe blooms observed in several intermediate years, i.e., 2012, 2016, 2018, 2020, and 2022 (Fig 2B).

The high-resolution bins also allow for detailed analysis of blooms in individual counties (Fig. 3B–E), providing insight into when site-specific blooms occurred and how individual counties contributed to overall bloom severity. For example, the 1957 bloom was widespread (>5,000 cells L⁻¹) across all counties, but severe blooms (>1,000,000 cells L⁻¹) were primarily confined to Pinellas County. Another example is from 2007 to 2014, and in 2019, when

blooms were not recorded in Pinellas, but did occur in the other counties, confirming the spatially patchy nature of the blooms. Additionally, in 2022 other counties experienced much more intense blooms than in 2021, whereas in Pinellas the 2021 bloom was stronger than that of 2022.

Respiratory irritation impact (RI) index for Sarasota and Manatee Counties. The RI index (Fig. 4A) was defined by the number of beach days for each respiratory irritation condition (present or slight, moderate, and high or severe, respectively) and normalized to the month/year with the most beach days. The monthly RI shows that the most severe respiratory irritation occurred in winter 2018. Moderate RI levels were recorded in summer–fall 2021, fall 2022–spring 2023, and fall–winter 2006/2016. The annual RI index (Fig. 4B) reached its maximum in the bloom year 2018 (10), followed by 2022 (5.9), and 2016 (5.6). In contrast, the RIs in 2007–2011, 2013–2014, and 2023 were almost negligible (< 1), while the 2010 bloom season (a bloom-free year) showed no reported respiratory irritation.

Fig. 5. This graph shows the relationship between the annual, bloom year, Respiratory Irritation impact (RI) index and the annual Bloom Severity Index (BSI). Many years showed negligible BSI or RI (2007, 2008, 2010, 2014, and 2023), or only slight blooms (2009, 2013, and 2011). Colors indicate onshore wind frequency, obtained from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration VENN1 wind station, at Venice, Sarasota County) from November of each year through next February, with gray squares indicating years with no wind observations. Circle size represents the average wind speed for each year. The black dashed line shows the linear regression between the two indices.

Coherence between BSI and RI. The coherence between the BSI and RI was previously examined [8]. The results showed that, at the monthly scale, *K. brevis* blooms and associated respiratory irritation were correlated, with RI values increasing during more intense blooms. However, because earlier BSI analyses were conducted across the entire southwest Florida region, they were not site- or county-specific. This may have introduced spatial aliasing between bloom observations and reports of irritation impacts. In this study, we narrowed the BSI and RI analysis to Sarasota and Manatee counties (Fig. 4), which have the longest and most complete datasets. We plan to provide annual updates of the indices by county. For simplicity, the present analysis focused on interannual timescales, where the two indices show coherent variability. This allowed us to examine the RI compared to different severity thresholds (Fig. 4). In general, blooms exceeding >50,000 cells L⁻¹ are associated with mild to moderate respiratory irritation impacts [10]. At the county level, the previously reported relationship between BSI and RI [9] remains valid (Fig. 5). A linear relationship exists between BSI and RI, but it is influenced by variability in onshore wind frequency (Fig. 5). More frequent onshore winds substantially increase the RI relative to BSI, as seen in 2018. Less frequent onshore winds (2006, 2015) result in a lower RI compared to BSI. An exception occurred in 2012, when RI was lower than expected despite frequent onshore winds, likely due to relatively low wind speeds in 2012 (Fig. 5). These results confirmed that: (1) County-specific BSI and RI are well correlated; (2) Irritation impact was only observed when blooms exceeded 50,000 cells L⁻¹; (3) Increased onshore wind frequency augmented irritation impact in most years.

Are low K. brevis cell concentrations (>5,000 cells L⁻¹) predictive of the occurrence of high-density blooms that can cause respiratory irritation? The analysis revealed that when >5,000 cells L⁻¹ occur in a given 0.15° latitude bin, there is a 71% probability that >50,000 cells L⁻¹ would also be observed during the same month (Table 1). In addition, 61% of these events were accompanied by blooms of > 100,000 cells L⁻¹. This sug-

gests that the presence of a low concentration bloom (>5,000 cells L⁻¹) in a given location, is often an indicator of bloom densities sufficient to cause mild to moderate respiratory irritation. In contrast, only 24% of the time did concentrations of >1,000,000 cells L⁻¹ occur in the same bin where >5,000 cells L⁻¹ had been recorded. Thus, the most intense blooms are not readily predictable based solely on the detection of lower-density blooms.

The methods used in this study can be updated annually to help managers estimate the likelihood of local communities being affected by blooms once low cell concentrations are detected. They also provide an overall probability of bloom impacts at the community level, aiding in contingency planning. This binning strategy may also prove useful in other regions where routine monitoring is conducted.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Aspen Cook at Mote Marine Lab for providing the Beach Condition Reporting System data. We are also indebted to Laura Markley at Florida Fish and Wildlife Research Institute for generously providing the cell count data from the FWC HAB Monitoring Database. VENT1 Wind data comes from NOAA NDBC (https://www.ndbc.noaa.gov/station_page.php?station=venf1). BK was supported by NOS/NCCOS #NA20NOS4780194 MERHAB19: Implementing *Karenia brevis* Respiratory Risk Forecast System in the Gulf of Mexico.

References

1. Steidinger KA & Joyce JEA 1973. Florida Red Tides. State of Florida Department of Natural Resources Educational Series No. 17, St. Petersburg FL.
2. Stumpf RP et al 2008. Cont Shelf Res 28(1):189–213. doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2007.04.017
3. Fleming LE et al 2009. Environ Health Persp 117(7):1095–1100. doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0900673
4. Fleming LE et al 2011. Harmful Algae 10(2):224–233. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2010.08.006
5. Kirkpatrick B et al 2010. Harmful Algae 9(1):82–86. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2009.08.005
6. Morgan KL et al 2010. Harmful Algae 9(3):333–341. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2009.12.004

7. Hoagland P et al 2009. Environ Health Persp 117(8):1239–1243. doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0900645
8. Landsberg JH et al 2009. Harmful Algae 8(4):598–607. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.11.010
9. Stumpf RP et al 2022. PLoS One 17(1):e0260755. doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0260755
10. Stumpf RP et al 2009. J Mar Syst 76(1–2):151–161. doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2008.05.016

Authors

Yizhen Li & R Wayne Litaker, CSS Inc. Under Contract to National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Ocean Service, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science, Silver Spring, MD, USA

Richard Stumpf, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Ocean Service, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science, Silver Spring, MD, USA

Barbara Kirkpatrick, Gulf of America Coastal Ocean Observing System Regional Association, Department of Oceanography, College Station, TX, USA

Katherine Hubbard, Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, St. Petersburg, FL, USA

Katherine Kohler Harrison, Gulf of America Alliance, Ocean Springs, MS, USA

Email corresponding author:
Yizhen.Li@noaa.gov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220214>

Seeing Blooms in a New Light: Digital Holography for HAB Monitoring in Lake Erie

Cyanobacteria-driven harmful algal blooms (cHABs) form a significant fraction of all HABs in freshwater systems globally. Among the Laurentian Great Lakes of North America, Lake Erie experiences severe cHAB events, comprising multiple toxic strains of different genera and species, including but not limited to, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Planktothrix aghardii*, and *Dolichospermum* sp.

The need for water-quality monitoring to safeguard human and aquatic ecosystem health has driven funding for comprehensive monitoring programs, through a combination of ship-based routine sampling, e.g., programs led by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's Great Lakes Environment Research Laboratory (NOAA GLERL), and the development of monitoring nodes at fixed locations across the lake. In parallel, there is also a constant endeavor to develop improved and state-of-the-art tools that can be

integrated into future routine monitoring needs.

Rapid strides in imaging technologies have made them an attractive prospect for in situ (or ship-board) plankton observations, including HAB-focused research, as evidenced by the popularity of the commercially available Imaging Flow Cytobot over the past decade [1–2]. Another promising imaging technique, digital holography, holds tremendous potential for HAB monitoring, with recent initial efforts proving promising [3]. Here, we report on field deployments and testing of an *in situ* holographic imaging system (AUTOHOLO) for monitoring cHABs in the western basin of Lake Erie.

Holography is a method that captures interference patterns resulting from the interaction of an undisturbed reference beam and diffracted light scattered by particles within a sample volume illuminated by a coherent light

source, such as a laser beam [4]. The resulting hologram encapsulates information about the size, shape and position of particles or organisms present in the sampling volume, which can be fully recovered during post-processing.

The AUTOHOLO, custom-built at Florida Atlantic University, has been previously used successfully in several applications, including documenting *Karenia brevis* blooms in the Gulf of Mexico [3]. Its versatile design incorporates flexibility in the optical arrangement to tune the system for specific applications. For example, while the standard operation mode uses a lensless configuration, the addition of a microscope objective in the optical path enables adaptive resolution; resolvable size ranges can vary from a few tens of microns to ~ 2 cm, depending on the optics. Additionally, the variable sampling length (1–20 cm) allows for adjustment of the sample volume based on the particle load/turbidity of the water column.

The geographical focus of the study was the western part of Lake Erie, further sub-divided into three areas of interest: the Detroit River (DR) outflow,

Fig. 1. (A). Map of western Lake Erie, with the three sub-regions where sampling was undertaken highlighted – (1) Detroit River outflow, (2) Western basin transect, and (3) nearshore Maumee Bay; (B). the custom-built *in situ* digital holographic microscope (AUTOHOLO) used in the study; and (C). Field deployment work at Lake Erie.

Fig. 2. (A). Morphological variability of *Microcystis aeruginosa* colonies (small to large); and (B). Collage of various planktonic organisms and non-living (sedimentary) particles from Lake Erie during pre- and peak-bloom periods, captured using our holographic imaging (AUTOHOLO) system.

Western Basin (WB), and the Maumee Bay region (Fig. 1a). The AUTOHOLE (Fig. 1b) was deployed in various modes (point sampling, vertical profiling and buoy-based) to quantify particle abundance and plankton community composition over multiple separate field efforts across 2022–2024. Each campaign (Fig. 1c) was carried out in pre-bloom (early summer, June), peak-bloom (August/September) or post-bloom (October) periods, to characterize the seasonal differences. The deployments focused primarily on two objectives: (a) the deployment and testing of the AUTOHOLE under different conditions and sampling the Lake Erie plankton communities, with a focus on *Microcystis sp.*; and (b) building a Lake Erie specific particle/plankton database to facilitate development of an automated data processing pipeline.

Particle abundances and community composition varied seasonally. During the early summer pre-bloom phase, *Microcystis sp.* was absent as expected; zooplankton (copepods, daphnia), certain diatom species, and non-living (sedimentary) particles were the most frequently observed groups. In August (peak bloom), cyanobacterial species, particularly *Microcystis aeruginosa*, dominated the Western Basin region, with other groups contributing negligibly. *Planktothrix aghardii* and *Dolichospermum sp.* were also frequently observed. Collages of observed *Microcystis* colonies of varying shapes/sizes, along with commonly observed particles and organisms in the datasets, are shown in Fig. 2a and 2b respectively.

Vertical profiles at different transects through the Western Basin re-

vealed decreasing *Microcystis sp.* concentrations with distance from shore, qualitatively consistent with satellite maps of bloom extent over the same time period. Ongoing processing of the data will enable us to: (i) characterize size distributions of *Microcystis* colonies; (ii) resolve high-resolution vertical and temporal variations in the spatial distributions of *Microcystis* colonies; and (iii) examine seasonal trends in plankton community composition, which are expected to shed further light on cyanobacterial ecology in the region.

This study demonstrates the ability of digital holography to detect and quantify HAB-forming (and other planktonic) species abundance in a range of diverse conditions in aquatic systems. While the simplicity of holography offers a compelling approach for in situ HAB monitoring, as with other in situ imaging approaches, bottlenecks and challenges remain in large-scale adoption, especially in remote operations and real-time monitoring networks. Some examples of limitations include data-intensive imagery restricting data transmission rates, biofouling of viewing windows, and reliable species-level classification of observed organisms. Future developments should focus on the integration of lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures for near real-time data processing [5–7].

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to the Great Lakes Observing System (GLOS) for funding support. Additionally, field and logistics support from Steve Ruberg at

NOAA GLERL and Bob Shuchman and Zane Almquist at Michigan Tech Research Institute was also instrumental in this effort.

References

1. Zheng B et al 2023. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 120(36):e2304590120. doi:10.1073/pnas.2304590120
2. Kraft K et al 2021. *Front Mar Sci* 8:594144. doi:10.3389/fmars.2021.594144
3. Barua R et al 2023. *Harmful Algae* 123:102401. doi:10.1016/j.hal.2023.102401
4. Nayak AR et al 2021. *Front Mar Sci* 7:572147. doi:10.3389/fmars.2020.572147
5. Göröcs Z et al 2018. *Light Sci Appl* 7:66. doi:10.1038/s41377-018-0067-0
6. Guo B et al 2021. *Limnol Oceanogr Methods* 19(1):21–36. doi:10.1002/lom3.10402
7. Sanborn D et al 2023. *Biotechnol Bioeng* 120(5):1399–1410. doi:10.1002/bit.28338

Authors

Ahammad Abdullah & Aditya R Nayak, Department of Ocean and Mechanical Engineering, Florida Atlantic University, 777 Glades Rd, Boca Raton, FL, USA; Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute, Florida Atlantic University, 5600 US 1 North, Fort Pierce, FL, USA

Timothy S Moore, Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute, Florida Atlantic University, 5600 US 1 North, Fort Pierce, FL, USA

Karl R Bosse & Michael J Sayers, Michigan Tech Research Institute, Michigan Technological University, 3600 Green Ct STE 100, Ann Arbor, MI, USA

Email corresponding author: anayak@fau.edu

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220224>

Lingulaulax polyedra bloom in the Port of Tomis, Romania

Fig. 1. Map of the bloom location.

The Port of Tomis is situated in the city of Constanța, along the western coast of the Black Sea in Romania (Fig. 1). This marina is popular for both fishing and recreational vessels and often attracts tourists and locals alike. Its semi-enclosed waters, enriched with nutrients

and influenced by human activity, provide conditions that can favour algal blooms.

Aquaculture in the Romanian Black Sea region has not reached its full potential due to environmental constraints and an unclear legislative framework.

However, despite these challenges, there is a growing interest in developing mussel and fish aquaculture, driven by the rising demand for seafood and the potential economic benefits it offers [1].

From October 19 to 28, 2024, an unusual water discoloration was observed in the area. This phenomenon was marked by a reddish-brown tint on the surface waters during the day. At night, the bloom became particularly remarkable; when the water was disturbed, it produced a bright blue bioluminescence (Fig. 2). The phenomenon quickly attracted local attention and was soon reported by the media. Microscopic analysis of water samples revealed the dominance of *Lingulaulax polyedra*, an armoured marine dinoflagellate (Fig. 3). This single-cell organism is commonly found in coastal waters and is known for producing a blue nighttime glow, a phenomenon called bioluminescence. Inside the cells, special organelles called scintillons contain the enzyme luciferase and its substrate luciferin. When the water is disturbed, a chemical reaction is triggered that releases a brief flash of blue light, making the sea sparkle at night. The function of this glow is still debated. Scientists suggest it may serve as a defence mechanism, either startling predators or attracting larger predators to feed

Fig. 2. *Lingulaulax polyedra* bloom during the day (A) and at night (B).

Fig. 3. Micrograph of *Lingulaulax polyedra* from a sample collected on October 21, 2024.

Fig. 4. Cyst of *Lingulaulax polyedra* (=Lingulodinium machaerophorum).

on grazers (the “burglar alarm” theory) [2]. Others believe it could be a stress response, triggered by mechanical or chemical changes in the environment [3–4]. So, the spectacular glow in the Port of Tomis was basically millions of dinoflagellates flashing their tiny “alarm lights” every time the water was disturbed. At the end of a bloom, resistant cysts were formed (Fig. 4), that set-

tle into the sediments until favourable conditions return [5]. Although *L. polyedra* has been previously recorded along the Romanian Black Sea coast, it usually occurs only rarely and at low abundances. However, during this event, densities exceeded 7×10^6 cells·L⁻¹.

Similar occurrences of red tides caused by *L. polyedra* have also been reported elsewhere in the Black Sea.

Notably, these phenomena were observed in Varna Bay (Bulgaria) during the warm months of 1987–1989, 1992 and in 2005, as well as in Odessa Bay (Ukraine) in September–October of 2020 [5].

Lingulaulax polyedra has been linked with the production of various toxins, including yessotoxins and ichthyotoxins, observed in multiple re-

Fig. 5. Bernd Krock, Oana Vlas and Andreea Gigiță collecting sediment samples.

gions worldwide. Despite this potential for toxicity, most red tide occurrences attributed to this species have not been directly linked to harmful effects [6]. Research on yessotoxins has shown significant gill damage in marine species due to epithelial cell degeneration and necrosis [7]. Although their effects on human health are not well understood, recent studies suggest yessotoxins may induce apoptosis in some tumour cell lines; other cardiotoxic and neurological effects were observed. Due to their potential risk to humans, yessotoxins (YTX) are one of the few groups of marine biotoxins regulated in seafood within the European Union. Regulation (EU) No. 786/2013 establishes a maximum permitted level of 3.75 mg YTX eq/kg [8]. However, only four variants are regulated and screened: YTX, 1a-homoYTX, 45-hydroxyYTX and 45-hydroxy-1a-homoYTX [9].

A previous toxin screening conducted in the Black Sea identified several variants of yessotoxins, other than the regulated ones, which most likely have a similar toxicity as YTX, but are not regulated or regularly screened. The low levels detected in previous studies indicate that the risk of acute intoxication in the western Black Sea was minimal [10], but the occurrence of such dense *L. polyedra* blooms like the one reported here may in fact pose a risk for the local seafood commercialization. There is a potential risk that YTX levels in seafood may exceed safe limits. This means that in the worst case, shellfish that are below the regulated YTX levels could carry a higher toxin load that might remain undetected and pose a

risk to consumers. Fortunately, there have been no incidents reported involving fish kills or instances of intoxicated shellfish linked to this bloom.

On June 19, 2025, researchers from the National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa” (NIMRD) and the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) collected sediment samples at the Port of Tomis (Fig. 5). These, along with a net sample that had been refrigerated from October 2024, were sent to the AWI laboratory for detailed analysis to detect cysts and potential toxins, important indicators for environmental health and food safety.

Future studies on this event will be approached in EX-AQUA [11], a Horizon Europe project that strengthens NIMRD’s role as a centre of excellence in marine algae aquaculture. By investigating *L. polyedra* bloom in the Black Sea, researchers are improving knowledge on harmful algal blooms (HABs), their recurrence potential, and toxin risks. In collaboration with AWI, advanced techniques such as cyst isolation, germination, culture establishment, toxin analysis, and genetic confirmation are being applied. These efforts contribute to EX-AQUA’s goals of enhancing HAB monitoring, supporting sustainable aquaculture, and laying the foundation for early warning systems in shellfish harvesting areas.

Acknowledgements

We thank our colleagues from AWI for their collaboration within the EX-AQUA project.

References

1. Niță V et al 2019. *Sci Pap-Ser D Anim S* 62(2):364–370.
2. Huang Y et al 2023. *Funct Ecol* 38(2):306–314. doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.14488
3. Von Dassow P et al 2005. *Limnol Oceanogr* 50(2):607–619. doi.org/10.4319/lo.2005.50.2.0607
4. Lewis J & Hallett R 1997. *Oceanography and Marine Biology*. In Gibson R N & M Barnes (Eds). CRC Press, London. pp. 89–153.
5. Klisarova D et al 2025. *Diversity* 17(2):105. doi.org/10.3390/d17020105
6. Prego R et al 2024. *Toxins* 16(6):280. doi.org/10.3390/toxins16060280
7. Pitcher GC et al 2019. *Harmful Algae* 81:30–41. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2018.11.006
8. Rubini S et al 2021. *Toxins* 13(9):634. doi.org/10.3390/toxins13090634
9. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) 2009. *The EFSA Journal* 1306:1–23. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2009.1306>
10. Dzhebekova N et al 2022. *Toxins* 14(10):685. doi.org/10.3390/toxins14100685
11. *Excellence and competitiveness in marine algae aquaculture for a sustainable Black Sea*; <https://ex-aqua.eu/>

Authors

Andreea Cristina Gigică, Oana Vlas & Laura Boicenco, National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa”, Romania

Bernd Krock, Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany

Email corresponding author: agigica@alpha.rmri.ro

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220249>

The benthic dinoflagellate genus *Prorocentrum* in five countries of Oceania

Diarrhetic shellfish toxin (DST) production has previously been found in benthic dinoflagellate species from the genus *Prorocentrum* and in planktonic dinoflagellate species from the genus *Dinophysis*. Details of the relationships between *Prorocentrum* species and their toxin production have not been fully elucidated in regions within Oceania. In this study, samples from five countries across Oceania (excluding Aotearoa New Zealand and the Rangitāhua Kermadec Islands; see [1]) were investigated.

Macroalgal (e.g., *Halimeda* spp. and *Padina* spp.) and seagrass (e.g., *Zostera* spp.) samples or epiphytes removed from the surface of macroalgae were collected into clear Ziplock bags, collection tubes, or plastic bottles by

hand and while snorkelling at sites in tropical/subtropical shallow coastal waters (<5 m depth) in 2003, 2014, 2018, and 2019 (Figs. 1 and 2): three sites in the Federated States of Micronesia, two sites in the Solomon Islands [2], one site in Niue [3], one site in the Cook Islands [4], and three sites in Australia [5–6]. Sample preparation procedures and the establishment of clonal isolates followed the methods described previously [1, 5–6]. Briefly, the isolates were maintained in sterile f/2–Si medium at 19 °C (for Australian strain SM43) or sterile metals mix SWII medium at 25 °C (± 2 °C) (for the other strains) under cool-white tube lights emitting approximately 60–90 μmol photons/m²/s with a photoperiod of 12:12 h (L:D).

Genetic experiments, including genomic DNA extraction, PCR of the large subunit ribosomal DNA (LSU rDNA) D1–D3 region, purification of the PCR amplicons, and sequencing for the established strains (except for the Australian strain SM43), were carried out according to the method described previously [1]. The experiments for strain SM43 followed the method described previously [5]. The sequences were aligned with reference sequences obtained from the DDBJ/EMBL/GenBank databases, and molecular phylogenetic analyses were performed using neighbour-joining (NJ) and maximum likelihood (ML) methods, as described previously [1]. The clade/subclade names of *P. lima* complex and *P. caipirignum*, as well as the rule for separating subclades based on at least one base pair change, which show different okadaic acid (OA) and dinophysistoxin-1 (DTX1) production characteristics, were used following a previous study [7].

Fig. 1. Sampling sites in this study. (A). Paiete Marine Park, Pohnpei, the Federated States of Micronesia. (B). Honiara, Guadalcanal Island, the Solomon Islands. (C). Titikaveka Beach, Rarotonga, the Cook Islands.

Fig. 2. Sampling and distribution map of 30 strains belonging to six benthic *Prorocentrum* species in five countries of Oceania. The numbers in each pie chart indicate the total number of clonal strains identified by molecular genetic methods. MPNi: Niho Marine Park, Pohnpei (6.943162, 158.169298). MPC: Paiete Marine Park, Pohnpei (6.982336, 158.200055). MPNe: Nett Point, Pohnpei (6.977970, 158.224998). B2RTH: Kinugawa Maru World War II ship wreck, Guadalcanal Island (−9.378672, 159.870754). NPHLB: Honiara, Guadalcanal Island (−9.430440, 159.991568). NMA: Avatele Beach, Makaapiapi (−19.126694, −169.913694). CIR: Titikaveka Beach, Rarotonga (−21.273333, −159.748056). RI: Raine Island, Queensland (−11.5903, 144.0350). HI: Heron Island, Queensland (−23.4423, 151.9148). MER: Merimbula, New South Wales (−36.8979, 149.9044).

DST analysis of all established strains, excluding strain SM43, cultured under the above conditions and harvested after approximately 50 days, was conducted for the ‘free’ and ‘total’ content of DSTs [OA, DTX1, and dinophysistoxin-2 (DTX2)] using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. The ‘esterified’ DST content was calculated by subtracting the ‘free’ content from the ‘total’ content. Details of the analysis have been described previously [1]. There was only ‘total’ DST content data available for strain SM43, which was cultured under the above conditions, harvested after approximately 20 days and analysed using the method outlined previously [8].

The Federated States of Micronesia: Eighteen benthic *Prorocentrum* strains were isolated from three sites, all within a kilometre of each other (MPNi, MPC, and MPNe), in 2018 (Fig. 1). They belonged to *P. lima* complex subclades 1a [number of strains (n) = 7], 1j (n = 4), and 1k (n = 3), *P. concavum* (n = 1), *P. cf. emarginatum* (n = 2), and *P. rathymum* (n = 1) (Figs. 2–3). Strains of *P. lima* complex subclade 1k

were established for the first time, and its subclade name is proposed in the present study (Fig. 3). The DST analysis revealed that the strains of *P. lima* complex subclades 1a, 1j, and 1k produced OA in the absence of DTX1 and DTX2. An isomer of DTX1 was detected as a very minor component in the strains of subclades 1a and 1k, but not in those of subclade 1j. The total DST cell quota of *P. lima* complex subclade 1a strains (19–44 pg/cell; total OA: 19–44 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0.093–0.16 pg/cell) tended to be higher than that of *P. lima* complex subclades 1j (14–19 pg/cell; total OA: 14–19 pg/cell) and 1k strains (19–22 pg/cell; total OA: 18–21 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0.66–0.84 pg/cell) (Fig. 4). All strains of *P. concavum*, *P. cf. emarginatum*, and *P. rathymum* did not produce any of the tested DSTs. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first report of the benthic *Prorocentrum* species in the Federated States of Micronesia.

The Solomon Islands: Four benthic *Prorocentrum* strains were isolated from two sites in 2018 (Fig. 1), and their sequences have been reported previ-

ously [2]. All strains belonged to *P. lima* complex subclade 1a (Figs. 2 and 3). These strains mainly produced OA, with DTX1 and the DTX1 isomer as minor components (total DSTs: 15–17 pg/cell; total OA: 11–15 pg/cell; total DTX1: 0.25–1.8 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0–2.6 pg/cell), in the absence of DTX2 (Fig. 4). Currently, the only recorded species in the Solomon Islands belongs to the *P. lima* complex.

Niue: Strains of benthic *Prorocentrum* isolated from a single site in 2018 were previously reported as *P. hoffmannianum*, identified by sequencing [3]. The present study reconfirmed the previous identification with phylogenetic analyses, showing that four strains belonged to that species, and revealed that they produced OA in the absence of DTX1, DTX1 isomer, and DTX2 (total OA: 13–25 pg/cell) (Figs. 2–4). Currently, the only recorded species in Niue is *P. hoffmannianum*.

The Cook Islands: One benthic *Prorocentrum* strain isolated from a single site in 2019 (Fig. 1) belonged to *P. concavum* and did not produce any tested DSTs (Figs. 2–3). Previously, two species (*P. lima* complex and *P. cf. maculosum*) have been reported based on morphological observations [9]. Therefore, the present study is the first record of *P. concavum* from the Cook Islands.

Australia: One benthic *Prorocentrum* strain isolated from Raine Island, Queensland in 2003 belonged to the *P. caipirignum* subclade b and produced OA without DTX1, the DTX1 isomer, or DTX2 (total OA: 51 pg/cell) (Figs. 2–4). Two strains isolated from Heron Island, Queensland and Merimbula, New South Wales in 2014 belonged to the *P. lima* complex subclade 1d and produced OA, with the DTX1 isomer as a very minor component, in the absence of DTX1 and DTX2 (total DSTs: 8.8–11 pg/cell; total OA: 8.8–11 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0.030–0.045 pg/cell) (Figs. 2–4). Previously, seven species (*P. clipeus*, *P. concavum*, *P. fukuyoi*, *P. hoffmannianum*, *P. lima* complex, *P. malayense*,

Fig. 3. Molecular phylogenetic tree of the benthic *Prorocentrum* species based on the LSU rDNA D1–D2 sequences (37 sequences, 657 positions) using the neighbour-joining (NJ) method. Strains in this study are shown in black and bold fonts. The analysis was conducted using the best DNA models, TN93 + G for NJ and TN93 + G + I for ML methods. Nodal support represents the NJ bootstrap value/maximum likelihood (ML) bootstrap value. Nodal support under 50 in NJ/ML is shown as a hyphen (-). A node that was not present in the ML tree is labelled as np. *1–5: Identical sequence(s) in each species or subclade. *6: Sequence determined previously [2]. *: Sequence determined in the present study but not registered. *8: Subclade proposed in the present study.

Fig. 4. Diarrhetic shellfish toxin (DST) profiles of the benthic *Prorocentrum* strains. (A). DST cell quota (pg/cell). (B). DST proportion (%). *1: A strain analysed for only total DSTs.

and *P. rhathymum*) were reported from Australia [10–11]. To the best of our knowledge, the present study is the first record of *P. caipirignum* from this country.

In conclusion, among the strains investigated in the present study, only strains belonging to the *P. lima* complex, *P. caipirignum*, and *P. hoffmannianum* were found to produce OA, DTX1, and/or DTX1 isomer, with varying toxin cell quotas. The DST cell quotas of a *P. caipirignum* subclade b strain from Australia and *P. lima* complex subclade 1a strains from the Federated States of Micronesia tended to be higher than those of the other strains of the *P. lima* complex and *P. hoffmannianum* from the other investigated locations. There are, therefore, potential risks to seafood safety caused by these DST-producing species in the investigated areas. Although the present study reported six benthic *Prorocentrum* species from these areas, the sampling effort was limited, and the number of established strains was small. It is, therefore, necessary to conduct further investigations into the diversity and toxin production of benthic *Prorocentrum* species to develop more robust baseline data and

to assess whether they pose a seafood safety risk in these areas.

Acknowledgements

The technical support of Sarah Challenger, Krystyna Ponikla, and Juliette Butler (Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae curators) was critical. The authors would like to give special thanks to Moses Pretrick and Margaret May Baekalia for their help collecting the samples in the Federated States of Micronesia, and David Ho’ota and Oliver Lukos for their help collecting the samples in the Solomon Islands. This research was conducted with funding from the New Zealand Seafood Safety research platform (contract number: CAWX1801), the Cawthron Institute Internal Capability Investment Fund, a postdoctoral fellowship from the JSPS Overseas Research Fellowships awarded to Tomohiro Nishimura, and a postdoctoral fellowship from the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey under a TUBITAK-BIDEB-2219-International Postdoctoral Research Fellowship awarded to Muharrem Balci (contract number: 1059B191800400).

References

- Nishimura T et al. Harmful Algae: under review.
- Murray S et al 2018. Sampling for benthic dinoflagellates in the Solomon Islands. In Reguera B & Bresnan E (Eds) HAN 61, UNESCO, pp. 11–12. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109858
- Butler J et al 2019. Epiphytic dinoflagellates from Niue, South Pacific Ocean. In Reguera B & Bresnan E (Eds) HAN 62, UNESCO, pp. 18–19. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109823
- Rhodes L et al 2020. Toxin profiles of *Gambierdiscus lapillus* from the Cook Islands. In Reguera B & Bresnan E (Eds) HAN 65, UNESCO, pp. 10–11. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109749
- Murray S et al 2014. Harmful Algae 39:242–252. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2014.08.003
- Larsson ME et al 2018. Mar Drugs 16(1):7. doi.org/10.3390/md16010007
- Nishimura T et al 2020. Harmful Algae 96:101687. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101687
- Verma A et al 2019. Toxins 11(10):571. doi.org/10.3390/toxins11100571
- Rhodes LL et al 2010. Toxicon 56(5):751–758. doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2009.05.017
- Murray S et al 2009. Protist 160(2):245–264. doi.org/10.1016/j.protis.2008.12.004
- Hoppenrath M et al 2023. Senckenberg Bücher Series 88: ISSN 0341-4108.

Authors

Tomohiro Nishimura, Fisheries Technology Institute, Japan Fisheries Research and Education Agency, 2-17-5 Maruishi, Hatsukaichi, Hiroshima 739-0452, Japan

J Sam Murray, Lesley L Rhodes, Kirsty F Smith & Lucy Thompson, Cawthron Institute, 98 Halifax Street East, Nelson 7010, New Zealand

Muharrem Balci, Biology Department, Faculty of Science, Istanbul University, Istanbul 34134, Turkey

Michaela E Larsson, Climate Change Cluster, Faculty of Science, University of Technology Sydney, 15 Broadway Ultimo, Sydney, New South Wales 2007, Australia

Arjun Verma, Shauna A Murray, School of Life Sciences, University of Technology Sydney, 15 Broadway Ultimo, Sydney, New South Wales 2007, Australia

Emails corresponding authors: nishimura_tomohiro49@fra.go.jp sam.murray@cawthron.org.nz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220260>

Harmful phytoplankton in Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta: The Largest Lagoon-Delta Ecosystem in the Colombian Caribbean

Fig. 1. Location of the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta (CGSM), Colombia.

Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta (CGSM) has been identified as one of the most productive coastal ecosystems at Neotropical latitudes [1]. Situated on the Caribbean coast of Colombia (Fig. 1), the wetland is bordered to the west by the Magdalena River, from which it originated. This river is regarded as the largest in the country and one of the most significant in Latin America. To the east, the CGSM lies adjacent to the foothills of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, the world's highest coastal mountain range (5,800 m above sea level). At the easternmost point of its northern boundary, an inlet measuring 120 m in width and 10 m in depth, provides a direct connection between the lagoon and the Caribbean Sea. The ecosystem is dominated by rivers and characterized by a dry climate with a microtidal regime (20 to 30 cm). Annual temperatures range from 27°C to 40°C, with low average annual precipitation (531 mm) and high evapotranspiration (1,800 mm). Relative humidity varies from 77% to 83%. The strong northeast

trade winds play a key role in maintaining high productivity throughout the year. The elevated biological productivity of CGSM (990 g C m² yr⁻¹) [2] supports seven fishing communities, collectively hosting around 20,000 people, of whom approximately 3,200 depend on fishing as their primary livelihood.

The CGSM is recognized as an Important Area for the Conservation of Birds and Biodiversity (AICA/IBA) and hosts two National Natural Parks, designated in 1964 and 1977. It has held international recognition as a Ramsar Site since 1998 and as UNESCO Biosphere Reserve since 2000. In 2017, it was added to the Montreux Record, highlighting its status as a wetland whose ecological character is under significant threat [3].

The high primary productivity that sustains populations of ecologically and commercially valuable fish and invertebrates is driven by phytoplanktonic groups. Over the past two decades, artisanal fishers have harvested between 4,178 and 9,269 tons of fish, contributing an average of 35% to the total

small-scale catches in the Caribbean region [4]. The phytoplankton community comprises approximately 578 taxa, distributed among cyanobacteria (69), centric diatoms (98), pennate diatoms (191), dinoflagellates (58), chlorophyta (81), euglenophyta (64), and other groups (17) [5].

The lagoon-delta complex has been subject to various environmental stresses over almost a century, including freshwater diversion, large-scale mangrove die-off, fish kills, water contamination, and biodiversity loss [6]. Given its ecological, social, and economic importance, CGSM is one of the most studied marine socio-ecological systems in Colombia with over 1,800 bibliographic references (<https://cgsm.cemarin.org>). The ecosystem has also attracted considerable media attention, with over 874 news articles published in the last three decades, nearly 10% of which focused on mass fish kills [3]. The mortality events have often been explained by a eutrophication model, in which anoxia caused by massive plank-

Table 1. Toxic species found in Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta.

Species	Associated Toxins	Habitat
<i>Chrysosporium (Anabaena) bergii</i> (Ostenfeld) E. Zapomelová, O. Skácelová, P. Pumann, R. Kopp & E. Janecek 2012	Anatoxins, Cylindrospermopsins, Microcystins, Saxitoxins	Brackish
<i>Coelosphaerium kuetzingianum</i> Nägeli 1849	Neurotoxins, Hepatotoxins	Freshwater
<i>Raphidiopsis (Cylindrospermopsis) raciborskii</i> Aguilera, A., Berrendero Gómez, E., Kaštovský, J., Echenique, R. O. & Salerno, G. L. 2018	Cylindrospermopsins	Freshwater
<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i> (Kützing) Kützing 1846	Microcystins	Freshwater
<i>Planktothrix (Oscillatoria) planctonica</i> (Elenkin) Anagnostidis & Komárek 1988	Microcystins	Freshwater
<i>Raphidiopsis curvata</i> Fritsch F. E. & Rich M. F. 1930	Anatoxins, Cylindrospermopsins, Saxitoxins	Freshwater
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia pungens</i> (Grunow ex Cleve) G. R. Hasle 1993	Domoic acid	Marine
<i>Fibrocapsa japonica</i> Toriumi & Takano 1973	Reactive oxygen species, hemolytic compounds	Marine
<i>Alexandrium minutum</i> Halim 1960	Saxitoxins, neosaxitoxins, Gonyauloxins.	Marine
<i>Gonyaulax spinifera</i> (Claparède & Lachmann) Diesing 1866	Yessotoxin	Marine
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i> (Ehrenberg) F. Stein 1878	Okadaic acid	Marine
<i>Prorocentrum cordatum</i> (Ostenfeld) J. D. Dodge 1976	Fast Acting Toxins	Marine

ton growth is caused by increases in PO_4 [7].

Since other potential causes of fish mortality have not been thoroughly evaluated, the objective of this paper was to provide a comprehensive review of extant studies to identify which phytoplankton species reported in the CGSM since 1986 are potentially toxic. Of the 578 taxa reported, 12 are considered toxic; 11 appear in the IOC-UNESCO taxonomic reference list of harmful microalgae [Table 1], while *Coelosphaerium kuetzingianum* has been reported as potentially toxic to Spanish inland waters [8]. Eleven of the CGSM species are potentially toxic and 21 are classified as non-toxic harmful species [Table 2]. Additionally, six organisms were identified only at the genus level, and considered potentially harmful. Among the toxic species, six are freshwater cyanobacteria, four are dinoflagellates,

one is a diatom, and one is a raphidophyte (*Fibrocapsa japonica*), discovered in 2015 and associated with a fish kill in the CGSM.

The potential for these species to cause toxic effects in humans remains largely unexplored due to two factors. First, consumption of CGSM fishery products extends beyond the immediate region, obscuring the local impact. Second, the interface between public health and environmental management remains underdeveloped, hindering effective communication and collaboration. In Colombia, harmful algal blooms (HABs) are not considered a significant threat and receive limited attention, in contrast to the expansion of road infrastructure and planned management initiatives for the CGSM. Given the ecosystem's importance for fisheries, rigorous monitoring is necessary to ensure the safety and quality of its products.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Universidad Nacional de Colombia for the opportunity to conduct research in the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta and to CEMarin for logistical support.

References

1. Cloern JE & Jassby AD 2008. *Ecol Lett* 11:1294–1303.
2. Hernández CA & Gocke K 1990. *An Inst Invest Mar Punta de Betín* 19:101–119. <https://boletin.invemmar.org.co/ojs/index.php/boletin/article/view/430>
3. Salzwedel H & Mancera-Pineda JE 2023. *The Colombian Ecoregion Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta in the Public Media, 1990-2020. Editorial Unimagdalena, Santa Marta.* 82 p.
4. Rodríguez-Rodríguez JA et al 2016. *The Wetland Book II: Distribution, Description and Conservation. In Finlayson CM et al (Eds). Springer Science+Business Media BV, The Netherlands.* https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6173-5_126-1.
5. Vidal LA 2010. *Manual del fitoplancton hallado en la Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta y cuerpos de agua aledaños. Fundación Universidad Jorge Tadeo Lozano Bogotá,* 384 p.
6. Botero L & Salzwedel H 1999. *Ocean Coastal & Management* 42:243–256.
7. Santos-Becerra LF et al 2025. *Calibration and validation of the Aerobic Mortality Risk Index (IRMA): an index for predicting mass mortality of fish due to anoxia. In Reguera B & Mertens KN (Eds) HAN 78, UNESCO, pp. 8– 9.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14883641>
8. Cirés S & Quesada A 2011. *Catálogo de cianobacterias planctónicas potencialmente tóxicas de las aguas continentales españolas. Dirección General del Agua de la Secretaría de Estado de Medio Rural y Agua del Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, y Medio Rural y Marino.* 85 p.

Authors

José Ernesto Mancera Pineda, Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Sede Bogotá, Colombia.

Edgar Arteaga Sogamoso (Independent investigator), Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Sede Caribe, Colombia & Horst Salzwedel.

Email corresponding author:
jemancerap@unal.edu.co

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220270>

Table 2. Potentially toxic species, genera and harmful non-toxic species found in Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta.

	Species/Genera	Associated Toxins	Habitat Marine (M) Freshwater (F) Brackish (B)
T O X I C	<i>Alexandrium cf. kutnerae</i> (Balech) Balech 1985	unknown	M
	<i>Alexandrium cf. minutum</i> Halim 1960	Saxitoxins	M
	<i>Anabaena cf. sphaerica var. tenuis</i> G. S. West 1907	unknown	F
	<i>Anabaena cf. spiroides</i> Klebahn 1895	Anatoxin-a	F
	<i>Dolichospermum (Anabaena) cf. spiroides</i> (Klebahn) Wacklin, L. Hoffmann & Komárek 2009	Anatoxins	F
	<i>Anabaenopsis cf. cunningtonii</i> W. R. Taylor 1932	unknown	F
	<i>Gonyaulax cf. diegensis</i> Kofoid 1911	unknown	M
	<i>Gonyaulax cf. rotundata</i> Rampi 1952	unknown	M
	<i>Microcystis cf. viridis</i> (A. Braun) Lemmermann 1903	Microcystins	F
	<i>Planktothrix (Oscillatoria) cf. agardhii</i> (Gomont) Anagnostidis & Komárek 1988	Microcystins, Anatoxin, Saxitoxins.	F
	<i>Planktothrix cf. isothrix</i> (Skuja) Komárek & Komárková 2004	Microcystins, Anatoxin, Saxitoxins	F
	<i>Aphanizomenon sp.</i>	Anatoxin, Saxitoxins, Cylindrospermopsins	F
	<i>Coelosphaerium sp.</i>	Neurotoxins, Hepatoxins	F
	<i>Cylindrospermopsis sp.</i>	Cylindrospermopsins	F
	<i>Cylindrospermum sp.</i>	Cylindrospermopsins	F
	<i>Phormidium sp.</i>	Alkaloid	F
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia sp.</i>	Domoic acid	M	
N O N -T O X I C	<i>Cerataulina pelagica</i> (Cleve) Hendey 1937		M
	<i>Protodinium cf. simplex</i> Lohmann 1908		M, F
	<i>Tripos furca</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez 2013		M
	<i>Chaetoceros tenuissimus f. beisugensis</i> Gogorev & Kovaleva 2010		M
	<i>Coscinodiscus centralis</i> Ehrenberg 1839		M
	<i>Guinardia striata</i> (Stolterfoth) Hasle 1996		M
	<i>Oxyrrhis marina</i> Dujardin 1841		M
	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i> Ehrenberg 1834		M
	<i>Sundstroemia setigera</i> (Brightwell) Medlin 2021		M
	<i>Anabaenopsis circularis</i> (G. S. West) V. V. Miller 1923		F
	<i>Anabaena oscillarioides</i> Bory ex Bornet & Flahault 1886		M, F
	<i>Anabaena sphaerica</i> Bornet & Flahault 1886		F
	<i>Anabaena torulosa</i> Lagerheim ex Bornet & Flahault 1886		M, F
	<i>Lynghya martensiana f. rupestris</i> Frémy 1930		M, B
	<i>Microcystis densa</i> Schiller 1956		F
	<i>Microcystis marginata</i> (Meneghini) Kützing 1846		F
	<i>Microcystis robusta</i> (H. W. Clark) Nygaard 1925		F
	<i>Gonyaulax digitalis</i> (Pouchet) Kofoid 1911		M
	<i>Gonyaulax polyedra</i> F. Stein 1883*		M
	<i>Gonyaulax scrippsae</i> Kofoid 1911		M
<i>Sourniaea diacantha</i> (Meunier) H.Gu., K.N.Mertens, Zhun Li & H.H.Shin 2020		M	

*) now *Lingulaulax polyedra* (F.Stein) M.J.Head, K.N.Mertens & R.A.Fensome 2024, can produce yessotoxins.

International Symposium on Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific, hosted in Aotearoa New Zealand.

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) represents a significant health concern in the Pacific region, especially in the South Pacific, where communities are heavily reliant on seafood for subsistence, income, and trade [1,2]. More than 80 % of the world's annual CP cases occur in the South Pacific region [3]. Since the first documented case in the 17th century, the incidence of CP has dramatically increased, though it is estimated that only

2–10% of cases are formally reported to health authorities [4].

CP is a growing threat to food security, livelihoods, and public health in Pacific communities, particularly as ocean temperatures rise and harmful algal blooms become more widespread. Many researchers and public health officials in Pacific Island Countries and Territories are keen to establish CP monitoring and surveillance programs;

however, limited funding and resources pose significant challenges, making CP a currently neglected disease in the Pacific. The detection of ciguatoxins in seafood and the dinoflagellate producers from the environment is extremely difficult and this also prevents the development and implementation of effective monitoring programs. Differences in available resources across nations highlight the necessity of understanding local needs and capabilities before undertaking research, ensuring devel-

Fig. 1. Attending members of the International Symposium on Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific held in Nelson, New Zealand, May 2025. Left to right: Back Row: MAC, PA, TJ, AS, LB, GG, ASel, KB, SM, HU, AT, AR, SMu, AM, MA, NO, TN, KS. Front Row: MC, TD, JL, TTA, TT, MF. Also absent from the photo: LR, EP, PH. See Table 1 for full names (alphabetical order) and institutions of all participants.

Fig. 2. Attending members during a tour of the Cawthron Institute's laboratories. Images: Cawthron Institute.

oped tools are effective and appropriate.

To address these issues, leading scientists, public health officials, and marine researchers from across the Pacific convened in Nelson, New Zealand, in May 2025 for the International Symposium on Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific. The event was hosted by the Cawthron Institute, with funding support from the French Embassy in New Zealand through a 'Fonds Pacifique' project developed in collaboration with CP experts from the Institut Louis Malardé in French Polynesia. The symposium marked the first international gathering on CP in the Pacific region since the 2008 International workshop on Ciguatera and Related Biotoxins held in New Caledonia.

This three-day workshop welcomed representatives from more than ten countries and territories, including New Zealand, French Polynesia, New Caledonia, Fiji, Tonga, Kiribati, Wallis

and Futuna, Vanuatu, the Cook Islands, Australia, and Japan (Fig. 1). Key topics covered included:

1. The current state of CP research and monitoring in Pacific nations
2. Cultural and social impacts of CP
3. Ecology of ciguatoxin producers such as *Gambierdiscus* species
4. Methods for ciguatoxins detection

Building on the momentum initiated in the frame of the Pacific Ciguawatch Initiative led by the Institut Louis Malardé [5], the symposium provided a vital platform for sharing scientific knowledge, tools, and traditional practices to enhance detection, surveillance, prevention, and response to CP.

The programme included field visits, lab tours (Fig. 2), and concluded with sessions dedicated to shaping future research directions and developing coordinated regional strategies for monitoring, predicting, and mitigating CP impacts. Participants also discussed potential for future collaborative fund-

ing opportunities and joint research initiatives.

The next step is to collaboratively draft a manuscript summarizing the symposium discussions and outlining priorities for future CP research. This publication will aim to highlight the importance of CP as a public health priority within the Pacific region.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the French Embassy in New Zealand for funding this symposium (a 'Fonds Pacifique' Grant was awarded to the authors in 2023), as well as the MBIE-funded Safe New Zealand Seafood Research Programme (contract No.: CAWX1801).

References

1. Lehane L & Lewis RJ 2000. *Int J Food Microbiol* 61:91–125. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(00\)00382-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(00)00382-2)
2. Chinain M et al 2021. *Harmful Algae* 102:101873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2020.101873>
3. Murray SA et al 2025. *Sci Total Environ* 994:179990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.179990>
4. Skinner MP et al 2011. *PLoS NTD*. 5:1416–1420. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0001416>.
5. Chinain M et al 2025. *Striving for a sustainable surveillance of Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific: the Ciguawatch initiative*. In Reguera B & Mertens KN (Eds) HAN 79, UNESCO, pp.6–8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15632917>

Authors

Laura Biessy & Kirsty F Smith, *Molecular and Algal Ecology, Cawthron Institute, Nelson, New Zealand.*

Mireille Chinain, H. Taiana Darius & Clémence Gatti, *Institut Louis Malardé, UMR 241-SECOPOL (IFREMER, ILM, IRD, Université de Polynésie française), French Polynesia.*

Email corresponding author:
Laura.biessy@cawthron.org.nz

Table 1. Full names (alphabetical order) of symposium participants and their institutions.

Initials	Full names	Institutions
AM	Alaric McCarthy	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
AR	Allan Rarai	University of the South Pacific, Fiji & links to Vanuatu
AS	Andreas Seger	SafeFish, Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies, Australia
ASel	Andy Selwood	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
AT	Aranteiti Tekiau	Ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources Development, Kiribati
EP	Emillie Passfield	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
GG	Greta Gaiana	UTS, Australia
HU	Hajime Uchida	Japan Fisheries Research and Education Agency, Japan
JL	Jimaima Lako	Fiji National University, Fiji
KB	Karine Brunet	Service de l'Environnement, Wallis & Futuna
KS	Kirsty Smith	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
LB	Laura Biessy	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
LR	Lesley Rhodes	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
MA	Masao Adachi	Kochi University, Japan
MAC	Mereana Atatoa Carr	Ministry of Marine Resources, Cook Islands
MC	Mireille Chinain	Institut Louis Malardé, French Polynesia
MF	Mele Faanunu	Ministry of Fisheries, Tonga
NO	Naomasa Oshiro	National Institute of Health Science, Japan
PA	Phoebe Argyle	Ministry of Marine Resources, Cook Islands
PH	Penny Harrison	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
SM	Sam Murray	Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
SMu	Shauna Murray	UTS, Australia
TD	Taiana Darius	Institut Louis Malardé, French Polynesia
TJ	Thierry Jauffrais	Ifremer, New Caledonia
TN	Tomohiro Nishimura	Japan Fisheries Research and Education Agency, Japan
TT	Takeshi Tsumuraya	Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan
TTA	Taarai Teetu Abere	Ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources Development, Kiribati

Sharing Italian Experience on Harmful Algae 2024/25 within BlueShellfish MCSA Staff Exchange

As part of the EU HORIZON Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action — Staff Exchange 101086234 — *BlueShellfish: Solutions to prevent and mitigate the impacts of HABs in Aquaculture and Fisheries in the context of global warming*, coordinated by CIIMAR (Portugal), a hybrid workshop entitled “Sharing Italian Experience on Harmful Algae: Challenges and Solutions to Prevent and Mitigate Their Impact on Human Health” was held on July 4th 2024 at the Department of Pharmacy, *University of Napoli Federico II* (Italy) (Figure 1). The event coincided with the first secondment of Dr Jorge Diogène and Dr Mònica Campàs from IRTA (Spain) at the UniNa.

The event, chaired by Prof. Carmela Dell'Aversano (UniNa, Italy) and Dr. Mònica Campàs (IRTA, Spain), brought together 16 invited speakers and over 65 participants (both in person and online) from Italy, Spain, UK, Norway, Turkey, and Brazil. It featured scientific presentations, thematic sessions, and a final round-table discussion on HAB management, with contributions from academia, environmental protection agencies, and public health experts. The workshop was part of WP2 *Development of highly sensitive tools for the early detection of toxins* – Task 2.5, focused on training and knowledge exchange in marine toxin analysis using advanced

instrumental and biosensing techniques. Practical fieldwork related to the workshop and to the secondment, also included sampling exercises in the Gulf of Naples (Fig. 2), at the Marine Protected Areas *Regno di Nettuno* (5 July 2024), which encompasses Vivara (zone A) and part of Ischia and Procida islands (zone B and C), the *Gaiola underwater park* (11 July 2024), and Procida Island (6 July 2024), with the support of Prof. Antonella Penna, President of the *Società Italiana di Biologia Marina*.

The workshop and related practical activities facilitated knowledge transfer between marine ecologists, marine biologists, and chemists, and allowed us to assess the presence of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* and ovatoxins (OVTXs) in bathing waters officially deemed safe and not under alert at the time. Macroalgal and seawater samples were collected during the sampling exercises and processed in the following months using two distinct and complementary chemical approaches: extraction and clean-up of intact toxins, and microscale oxidation, followed by LC-MS/MS analysis in Multiple Reaction Monitoring mode of both intact toxins and their oxidation products [1–2]. The chemical work was conducted mainly by Dr Chiara Melchiorre and the graduated MD student Martina Carelli, who will present the results at

the upcoming *21st International Conference on Harmful Algae* and the *XXXI Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica Analitica*, respectively.

As for the main results:

- OVTXs were detected at two sites: at Castello Aragonese left side (Ischia), zone B of Regno di Nettuno MPA, and at Gaiola, despite *Ostreopsis* cell concentrations being well below the 10,000 cells·L⁻¹ alert thresholds set by the Italian guidelines [3].
- At Castello Aragonese left side, OVTX concentration reached ~1,500 ppb, with a toxin profile typical of Mediterranean strains (OVTX-a, -b, -c, -d, -e).
- At Gaiola, only OVTX-a was identified and at lower abundance (~90 ppb).
- OVTXs were below detection limits in field samples from Vivara (Regno di Nettuno MPA, zone A) and Procida Island (Regno di Nettuno MPA, zone B), and could only be detected analytically when isolated *O. cf. ovata* strains were grown in culture.

These results suggest that *Ostreopsis*-related risk may be significantly underestimated when relying solely on cell counts, as is the current practice in Regional Monitoring Frameworks [3]. The production of OVTXs is strain-dependent and influenced by environmental conditions, meaning that even low cell numbers can coincide with high toxin levels. Additionally, the oxidative cleavage method [2], used to fragment toxins for structural confirmation, compared to the intact method [1] revealed some inconsistencies in toxin quantification. This highlights the analytical challenges

Fig. 1. Participants, organizers, and chairs of the BlueShellfish workshop held on July 4th 2024, at the Department of Pharmacy, University of Napoli Federico II.

posed by OVTXs, including matrix effects, adduct formation, and the need for certified reference materials.

This study, conducted within the BlueShellfish framework, confirms the urgent need for a toxin-focused monitoring strategy. Current cell-based thresholds may fail to reflect actual exposure risk, particularly through aerosol inhalation, dermal contact, or seafood ingestion. Symptoms caused by OVTX poisoning—such as fever, respiratory distress, and skin or eye irritation—are often mistaken for flu-like infections, making it difficult to accurately identify and report poisoning cases along the Italian coastline, including the Campania region.

Unfortunately, the absence of certified OVTX reference materials and validated LC-MS methods currently limits the reproducibility and comparability of results across laboratories. A new regulatory and methodological framework is essential to:

- Accurately quantify OVTXs in the environment and seafood chain;
- Develop certified standards and harmonized analytical protocols;
- Enhance public health response capabilities in concomitance with climate-driven HAB expansion.

Other tasks of Blueshellfish MCSA WP2 focus on the investigation of sustainable materials and devices for detecting toxins in seawater. Preliminary work has evaluated the efficiency of cyclodextrin (CD) polymers as passive sampling material for capturing of palytoxin-like compounds in seawater. This study was conducted by an interdisciplinary Italy-Spain team involving organic chemists, analytical chemists, chemical engineers and marine ecologists from UniNa, the University of Urbino, Universitat Rovira i Virgili and IRTA. Preliminary results of a study led by Prof. Luciana Tartaglione were encouraging, suggesting that various factors, including toxin concentration, sorbent material amount, and extraction time, all play an important role in the efficiency of toxin recovery from CD sorbents. The use of aptamers is also being explored as potential early-warning devices for toxins of highest concern for seafood consumers in Italy, such as Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning toxins. However, progress has been slower

Fig. 2. Moments from the sampling exercises conducted in July 2024 in the Gulf of Naples. (A) Gaiola Underwater Park; (B) Regno di Nettuno MPA.

than expected, as aptamer development has required investigation of the supra-molecular structures of selected oligonucleotides by High Resolution Mass Spectrometry, Circular Dichroism, and eventually NMR. This work, led by Prof. Michela Varra, is ongoing as part of the PhD project of Avazbek Abduvakhidov.

The BlueShellfish MCSA is ongoing at the University of Napoli Federico II, in close collaboration with WP2 leader Dr Mònica Campàs, combining research, fieldwork, and international collaboration to build a robust HAB risk mitigation system aimed to protect human and environmental health. Latest updates can be found at <https://blueshellfish.ciimar.up.pt/p173-team-pt>. A training course is foreseen at UniNa in 2026. Stay tuned!

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Prof. Antonella Penna and to Dr Silvia Casabianca for their invaluable contribution to the organization of the practical field activities within the BlueShellfish workshop. We also acknowledge the following funding sources:

HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-01 BlueShellfish “Solutions to prevent and mitigate the impacts of HABs in Aquaculture and Fisheries, in the context of global Warming” grant no. 101086234.

National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4 Component C2 Investment 1.1—Call for tender D.D. 104 of 2 February 2022 of the Italian Ministry of University and Research funded by the European Union—Next-GenerationEU, Award Number: Project code 2022KZLJZH, Concession Decree D.D. 1015 of 7 July 2023 adopted by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, CUP I53D23003260006, Project title: Emerging toxins in Italian seas and risks for human health (Tox-IT).

National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.4 - Call for tender No. 3138 of 16 December 2021, rectified by Decree n.3175 of 18 December 2021 of Italian Ministry of University and Research funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU. Project code CN_00000033, Concession Decree No. 1034 of 17 June 2022 adopted by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, CUP E63C22000990007, Project title “National Biodiversity Future Center - NBFC”.

Views and opinions expressed here-in are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

1. Ciminiello P et al 2015. *Anal Bioanal Chem* 407:1463–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-014-8367-6>.
2. Selwood AI et al 2012. *Toxicol* 60(5):810–820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicol.2012.05.024>.
3. Ministero della salute, I.S.P.R.A., *Linee guida: Gestione del Rischio Associato Alle Fioriture Di Ostreopsis ovata Nelle Coste Italiane, 2007*. Available at <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/files/alghe-tossiche/linee-guida-minsalute-ostreopsis.pdf>.

Authors

Carmela Dell'Aversano, Chiara Melchiorre, Luciana Tartaglione, & Michela Varra, Department of Pharmacy, University of Naples Federico II, Italy.

Jorge Diogène, & Mònica Campàs, Marine and Continental Waters, IRTA, Tarragona, Spain

Email Corresponding author (Carmela Dell'Aversano): dellaver@unina.it

New international project and opportunities for students and ECRs Phycotoxins in the Arctic marine ecosystem: an emerging climate change risk (PHATE)

The Arctic region is warming several times faster than the global average, leading to rapid changes in sea ice, ocean circulation, and ecosystem dynamics [1]. One emerging concern is the increasing frequency and magnitude of HABs in high-latitude waters. This has been documented in the Pacific Arctic [2], but important gaps exist for the Atlantic Arctic. Although HABs are expected to become more prevalent with climate change, our understanding of where, when, and how they will occur and their potential

impacts on food security and economic activities of local and indigenous communities is very limited.

To address this challenge, an ambitious new international project – PHATE (Marine Phycotoxins in the Arctic: an Emerging Climate Change Risk) – has been launched. PHATE is a multinational collaborative initiative funded under the Nordforsk call for *Sustainable Development of the Arctic* and coordinated by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) and the University

of New Brunswick (UNB), that brings together natural and social scientists, Inuit Knowledge Keepers, wildlife specialists, public health professionals, and policymakers. It involves 22 partners across Greenland, Canada, Iceland, the Faroe Islands, Denmark, and Norway.

Understanding the impacts of harmful algae on food security requires a comprehensive approach that integrates knowledge of large-scale ocean processes, ecological connectivity, phytoplankton dynamics, and trophic inter-

Fig. 1. The Arctic marine food web supports access to affordable and nutritious local and indigenous food systems and underpins the economies of northern societies. This project will investigate the climate-driven prevalence of toxigenic phytoplankton and their toxins, with focus on domoic acid (DA) and saxitoxins (STX).

actions, as well as downscaled models capturing local ecosystems and socio-economic perspectives (Fig. 1). To address this complexity, the project is structured around four interconnected work packages with strong regional relevance: 1) Monitoring and baseline data; 2) Phycotoxins in the Arctic marine ecosystem, 3) Food security and public health, and 4) Prediction, adaptation and resilience.

The project will integrate multiple approaches to build the first regional risk assessment for marine phycotoxins in the Atlantic Arctic. These include remote sensing, environmental monitoring, sedimentary ancient DNA, archaeological bioarchives, and community-based knowledge. A key innovation will be the development of new molecular tools to detect toxin biosynthesis genes in modern and ancient samples, allowing researchers to reconstruct the long-term history of toxigenic taxa such as *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Alexandrium*.

PHATE will also investigate how phycotoxins move through the Arctic marine food web – from plankton to fish, seabirds, and marine mammals – with a focus on species of cultural and subsistence importance to northern communities. By combining ecological data with cultural narratives and food practices, the project aims to co-develop tools that support early-warning systems, risk communication, and sustainable resource management under a changing climate.

Beyond advancing scientific understanding, PHATE places strong emphasis on capacity building and collaboration with local and Indigenous communities, ensuring that results are meaningful and useful at local, regional, and international levels. In Nunatsiavut, Nunavik, and Greenland, we are adopting a community-based research approach in which local stakeholders and right-holders play leading roles at every stage. PHATE is co-designed with local researchers, community members, and hunting organizations to ensure Inuit expertise guides the selection of sampling locations, animal species and specific tissues to examine (e.g., which species and parts are most consumed). A phased, pilot-monitoring program will begin in communities near local research centres to build capacity and develop effective logistical procedures for on-site use of detection technologies and sampling. Active local engagement will increase the likelihood of early detection and reporting of relevant environmental changes or signs of harmful algal blooms, enabling more timely and proactive responses from both management and public health perspectives.

Acknowledgements

This program is supported by NordForsk through the funding for Marine Phycotoxins in the Arctic: an emerging climate change risk (project number 215521) and the Government of Canada's New Frontiers in Research Funds (NFRF;

grant number NFRFJ-2024-00015). We also acknowledge support from ArcticNet and Genome Québec.

References

1. AMAP 2025. *Arctic Climate Change Update 2024: Key Trends and Impacts. Summary for Policy-makers. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)*, Tromsø, Norway, 16p.
2. Lefebvre KA et al 2025. *Nature* 644:693–698. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09230-5>

Authors

Sofia Ribeiro, Department of Glaciology and Climate, Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland and Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

Audrey Limoges, Department of Earth Sciences, University of New Brunswick, Canada

PHATE team members

Email corresponding authors:
sri@geus.dk
alimoges@unb.ca

PHATE has entered an active phase of recruitment, and there are several opportunities for students and early-career researchers at M.Sc., Ph.D., and postdoctoral levels to join the team. Contact us for more information.

Interview with Barrie Dale

Few scientists have had as profound an influence on the study of dinoflagellate cysts as **Barrie Dale**. From his first encounter with fossils as a child in England to his pioneering work at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution in the 1960s, Dale's career has consistently bridged the worlds of geology and biology. In 1966, he achieved a milestone moment when he documented the first hatching of a dinoflagellate cyst, linking microfossils with their living planktonic stages—an achievement he likened to “hatching a dinosaur egg.” This discov-

ery transformed our understanding of the fossil record, harmful algal blooms (HABs), and the evolutionary resilience of dinoflagellates.

Over the decades, Dale's work has spanned continents and disciplines: from incubating cysts in seabed sediments to tracing their ecological signals in climate reconstructions and eutrophication studies. His contributions laid the foundation for modern HAB research, influenced international monitoring practices, and inspired generations of young scientists. His career

embodies the “golden era” of oceanography, when curiosity-driven science reshaped entire fields.

In this interview with **Kenneth Mertens**, Barrie Dale reflects on his formative years, the evolution of cyst research, and the lessons he hopes will guide the next generation of scientists. His story is one of persistence, interdisciplinary vision, and a lifelong passion for uncovering the hidden lives of some of the ocean's most remarkable microorganisms.

Personal and Career Background

What initially sparked your interest in dinoflagellate cysts?

Geology. As a seven-year-old I stumbled upon fossil roots from a 300-million-year-old Carboniferous tropical forest near my home in England, and from that day on I decided to become a paleontologist. I aimed for a geology degree, but fortunately I failed one of my A level GCE exams, chemistry, and that disrupted my university plans. Instead of retaking the exam, I seized an opportunity to follow an alternative as a research technician in Sheffield University's geology department, a global leader in organic-walled microfossils (palynology). I developed techniques to dissolve rocks and expose ancient acritarchs—microplankton fossils thought extinct. This work introduced me to graduate student David Wall, who as a Post Doc at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) later invited me to join him in the search for living representatives of these fossils, which turned out to be dinoflagellate cysts¹.

How did you first encounter dinoflagellates at Woods Hole?

In the early-1960s paleontologist Bill Evitt showed morphological evidence suggesting that some fossil acritarchs were dinoflagellate cysts [1]; a time when almost all biologists did not realize dinoflagellates produced such cysts.

¹ Editor's note: When Barrie Dale refers to cysts in this interview, he means resting cysts, which are often the result of sexual processes.

My role at WHOI was to help discover living representatives of these fossils in seabed sediments, develop incubation methods, and hatch them to reveal their planktonic stages. One night in 1966, I hatched and photographed for the first time the excystment of one of these, *Spiniferites bentorii*, a species linked to a Cretaceous genus, and it produced a swimming *Gonyaulax digitalis* ([2], Fig. 1). This was a transformative moment, akin to hatching a dinosaur egg in the Arizona desert. It and subsequent in-

cubation experiments confirmed that many acritarchs were dinoflagellate resting stages, linking geological and biological information for the group. The excitement seeing this first one hatch was a high point in my career.

Who were the key mentors and collaborators shaping your work?

At Sheffield, Roger Neves (Carboniferous spores/pollen) and Charles Downie (marine palynology) introduced me to microfossils. At WHOI, Charlie Yentsch

Fig. 1. First dinoflagellate cyst hatching documented at Woods Hole in 1966.

tutored me in oceanography, Bob Guillard in culturing techniques [3], and Bill Berggren, a foraminifera expert, kept me grounded in micropaleontology. David Wall was a pivotal collaborator, as PI for our projects discovering living cysts; I was his research assistant/associate [4]. In Oslo, Trygve Braarud, Grethe Hasle, and Karen Gaarder offered plankton expertise, patiently answering my questions and inspiring my biogeography focus.

Can you elaborate on the 1972 New England HAB outbreak?

The first major recorded *Alexandrium* bloom along the Massachusetts coast caused shellfish toxicity (PSP), leading to beach closures to shell-fishing. At this time Canada was monitoring *Alexandrium* along their East Coast, following Mussel toxicity issues affecting troop rations in WWII, and Maine had robust monitoring, using plankton samples and mouse tests to detect rising cell numbers and toxicity. This was the first report of PSP spreading down the coast to Massachusetts, and recurring blooms have been recorded since. Interestingly, despite much HAB research the cause remains unknown. David Wall obtained an outbreak sediment sample, and we hatched *Alexandrium* cysts with red eyespots, confirming their role in HABs. This event catalyzed modern HAB research globally, with funding eventually fueling toxic cyst studies. Political pressure from affected coastal communities (e.g., politicians' summer homes) amplified its significance.

Why did you relocate to Oslo, and what did you achieve there?

I considered the next step was to study cyst-plankton relationships, just how representative of plankton is the cyst record? David Wall was directing his research back to fossil cysts in the Jurassic and my suggested project was deemed un-fundable in the U.S. The Oslo phytoplankton group with some of the longest interannual records generously invited me to join them in 1973 as a guest researcher to carry out my own project. Initially, I gave lectures at the four universities in Norway for a modest salary before applying for and securing funding from the Norwegian funding agency. In Dale, 1976 [5], I compared sediment cysts to several years of plankton data,

showing cysts represent multi-year plankton dynamics of approximately 20% of 55 plankton species. I greatly appreciated this opportunity to learn about living plankton ecology.

How did your early experiences influence your research philosophy?

My childhood fossil discovery instilled a sense of wonder about Earth's history and the details of the natural living world, shaping my research linking the two.

What role did the "golden era" of oceanography play in your work?

Post-WWII U.S. Navy funding aimed at "learning everything about the ocean", and this enabled our exploratory cyst research at WHOI in what Wally Broecker described in 1976 as "the golden era during which science was given a blank check by the public to pursue its whims" (Fig. 2). This freedom allowed us to pioneer hatching techniques and global distribution studies without immediate applied pressures, setting the stage for later HAB and environmental applications.

How did your role in HAB conferences shape the field?

I served on the Organizing Committees for many of the International HAB Meet-

ings and taught the first cyst workshop, at the Second of these in Florida, 1978. Some readers will happily remember a notable international conference, too, that I organized with the Sherkin Island Marine Station, Ireland, bringing together experts and young "experts-to-be" on HABs together with aquaculture interests, government agencies, and environmentalists in 1987 (Fig. 3). I always presented work at conferences, trying to bring a geological perspective to cysts in sediments.

How did your Oslo work build on WHOI findings?

At WHOI, we established cysts as living fossils and began to document their global distribution and ecological significance; in Oslo, I quantified how representative they are of ecology, showing cysts as reliable environmental indicators for paleoecology and HAB monitoring.

What personal impact did hatching the first cyst have on you?

I never "recovered" from the 1966 excystment of the first cyst [2] – it fueled my lifelong passion for sharing cyst research, driving my teaching and outreach efforts to inspire others in the field.

Fig. 2. Ready for decent on one of two of earliest dives for science with Alvin deep sea off US East Coast, early 70s.

Fig. 3. Barrie, Amy, and Karen Steidinger relaxing during the 3rd Sherkin International Conference on “The Problems of Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms in Aquaculture, Sherkin Island, 1989.

What lessons from your career can guide future cyst researchers?

Embrace interdisciplinary learning, persist through setbacks, and prioritize sharing knowledge. My career path—redirected by a failed exam and enriched by global collaborations—shows the value of adaptability and community fellowship in advancing science.

Any final reflections on your career?

I’m deeply grateful for the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award (HAB community) and the AASP Lifetime Achievement Award (paleontology), reflecting peer recognition for my efforts to bridge biology and geology. These honors are profoundly moving, affirming the value of interdisciplinary science.

Evolution of the Field and Research Challenges

What was your early work on cysts, and how did this help the field evolve?

At WHOI, we established for the first time that many cysts are dinoflagellate resting stages. We developed extraction and incubation methods, revealing well-preserved fossils and living forms. In 1968 we published the first paper linking living cysts to dinoflagellate phylogeny, and in 1977 we published the first ecological interpretations of global cyst distributions using FORTRAN punch-

cards and WHOI’s first computer in its own large room [6]. The 1972 New England *Alexandrium* HAB outbreak shifted focus to HAB cysts, and I published the first toxic *Alexandrium* cyst, from the Oslofjord [7]. Much of this work helped lay the groundwork for us and many others to develop the cysts into today’s substantial research field.

What do you consider your most significant contribution?

My work with David Wall at WHOI, particularly hatching and documenting the first cyst excystment in 1966, published in *Nature* as “living fossils”, was groundbreaking [2]. Together with co-authors, we discovered increased levels of toxicity in some *Alexandrium* cysts in Maine that could explain toxic shellfish in winter [8]. In Oslo, my students and I pioneered cysts as environmental indicators for eutrophication and pollution as significant tools for managing environmental degradation and recovery [14], and Amy Dale and I developed ecological models of recent cysts that proved successful for interpreting paleoecology back to Cretaceous Time in large biostratigraphic sequences ([9] shows a Paleocene example). On the personal level, I also include my efforts to help introduce many younger researchers to cysts through teaching workshops and seminars to research groups. I am proud to have helped some of the eminent scientists in the field today “find” cysts.

How has the study of dinoflagellate cysts evolved over your career?

Initially it focused on identifying cysts and their fossil status, the field expanded to global distributions, environmental applications, phylogeny (via molecular work), and applications in HABs, paleoceanography, and climate change. Early microscopy gave way to SEM, genetic barcoding, and AI-driven identification. Funding shifted from oil industry biostratigraphy to HAB research in the 1970s, then climate/paleoenvironmental studies were added, driven by societal priorities such as climate change. Anne de Vernal’s paleoceanographic models highlight the potential for cysts as climate proxies, despite challenges with quantitative accuracy. AI is revolutionizing taxonomy and cyst identification (e.g. a former student Robert Williams has digitized cyst slides with training programs to identify taxa [10]).

What challenges did you face in studying cysts?

Initially, moving to WHOI with no oceanographic training. These were fortunately the early days of modern oceanography – I don’t think there were oceanographic departments anywhere in universities, and the few oceanographers at WHOI were able and willing to help newcomers like me. Straddling biology and geology was demanding, requiring extensive literature review to include both. Institutional shifts, too: teaching marine geology while maintaining living cyst research in a phytoplankton department, or later the opposite challenges working in a geoscience department doubled my workload. Funding pressures increasingly favored applied research (HABs, climate, geo-industry), limiting basic science exploration. My research surely gained from dealing with such challenges.

What misconceptions about cysts persist in the scientific community?

Three stand out: (1) Cysts form primarily under adverse conditions—my evidence suggests they’re part of natural sexual cycles, often during population peaks when conditions are optimal; (2) All cyst morphology is functional—the incredible details of reflected morphology from thecae, for example, lack clear function; (3) Cysts form contractually inside thecal plates—development is

Fig. 4. Collecting sediment for a cyst survey of coastal waters of The United Arab Emirates for The Environment Agency, Abu Dhabi, 2011.

Scientific Aspects of Dinoflagellate Cysts

What environmental factors trigger cyst formation in dinoflagellates?

Lab studies suggest nutrient depletion or stress induces cysts, but natural triggers are less clear. Cysts likely form as part of sexual reproduction cycles, not solely in adversity. Field studies are needed to clarify how environmental factors interact with genetic and ecological drivers.

How do cysts contribute to harmful algal bloom (HAB) persistence?

Cysts anchor HAB species to a region, surviving in sediments for up to over a century, sometimes enabling recurrent blooms. For at least some species, cysts may be significantly more toxic than the motiles. However, blooms of known cyst-forming species don't always produce detectable cysts in the sedimentary record, as seen in an Abu Dhabi case (Dale & Dale, unpublished observations; Fig. 4), suggesting variable cyst production, resilience, or sampling challenges.

What is known about cyst dormancy and germination mechanisms?

Don Anderson and Jane Lewis' groups have provided foundational insights into dormancy and germination, but gaps remain, particularly for open-ocean species. Physiological triggers and survival mechanisms under extreme conditions (e.g., deep-sea pressure and low temperatures) are poorly understood.

Are there species with unique or surprising cyst dynamics?

Cosmopolitan species like *Protoceratium reticulatum* produce disproportionately high cyst numbers, aiding global distribution. Geologically, cysts enabled dinoflagellates to survive mass extinctions, highlighting their resilience and evolutionary significance.

Are there dinoflagellate species where cyst formation is not obligatory?

Yes, probably the majority. Particularly many open-ocean dinoflagellates likely rely on alternative survival strategies, as cyst formation is not universal.

more likely completed post-release, as seen in *Gonyaulax*, *Pentaparsodinium dalei* and *Lingulodinium* [13]. Literature with diagrams showing cysts with long processes inside complete thecae are misconceptions.

What are the biggest challenges facing cyst research today?

Funding is skewed heavily toward climate change and HABs, sidelining broader basic research. HAB prediction models have stalled, suggesting that a shift of emphasis to aquaculture monitoring is needed. Distinguishing details in environmental signals (e.g., eutrophication vs. climate) remains complex due to overlapping factors and sediment transport issues.

How do you see the future of cyst research evolving?

Funding will likely prioritize climate-driven research, potentially overshadowing other environmental issues such as pollution. HAB research momentum may decline as health-related funding for more pressing global crises competes. Promising areas include water quality bio-indicators, ballast water monitoring, and molecular/AI advancements, but basic science needs ever-more-protection from applied pressures.

Why is maintaining geo-bio connections important in cyst research?

The interplay between fossil records and living systems enriches our understanding of dinoflagellate evolution and ecology. Geological data provide deep-time context, while biological insights reveal modern dynamics, enabling more robust environmental reconstructions and predictions.

How do funding pressures affect cyst research today?

Climate and HAB priorities dominate funding, often at the expense of basic science such as cyst physiology or open-ocean dynamics. Researchers must balance societal demands with independent inquiry to preserve innovative discovery.

What makes dinoflagellates a "fantastic" group of organisms?

Single-celled yet exceptionally complex (eyes?), dinoflagellates exhibit diverse strategies—motility, predation, mixotrophy, and cyst formation—surviving extreme conditions and mass extinctions. Their evolutionary significance and ecological adaptability are awe-inspiring. There are probably few groups that can rival dinoflagellates for biological interest in the living and evolutionary potential of such a long and detailed fossil record.

How well do we understand cyst adaptations to extreme conditions?

We know little about how cysts survive conditions like prolonged darkness, high pressure, or near-freezing temperatures, especially in open oceans. Questions remain about sinking rates, floatation mechanisms, and density adaptations in deep water columns. Cyst formers in the open ocean must have alternative strategy than benthic resting stages.

How do cysts contribute to bloom forecasting?

Cysts indicate potential bloom initiation size but not bloom magnitude or fate, as water-column factors (e.g., currents, nutrients, predation, competition) dominate outcomes. The effective monitoring for HABs by John Hurst at the Maine Department of Marine Resources that I witnessed in the 1970s showed that it required almost daily plankton counts from strategic stations to follow a bloom for short term forecasting. It was not possible from counts in the initial population. Large cyst banks don't guarantee larger blooms, severely limiting long-term forecasting from cysts.

How reliable are cyst-based taxonomic classifications?

Morphological classifications are generally reliable when validated by genetics, despite some plasticity. Natural variation within species poses a greater identification challenge than plasticity itself.

What are the challenges in linking cysts to their motile counterparts?

Original descriptions often lack detail, and modern genetics/SEM reveal inadequacies. Creating new species names risks disconnecting from historical literature. I advocate re-sampling type localities to refine descriptions and maintain continuity. Also, the conflicts caused by "merging" geologically-based cyst species and biologically-based taxonomy are still avidly discussed after nearly sixty years.

How have molecular tools advanced cyst taxonomy?

Molecular analysis reveals genetic distinctions invisible morphologically, improving species delineation, and re-

vealing many new species. Barcoding enhances accuracy, though selecting appropriate genomic regions is critical for large dinoflagellate genomes. I hope they are using the appropriate ones.

Are there cryptic species distinguishable only by cyst morphology?

Likely, as seen in toxic/non-toxic *Alexandrium* strains, but identifying cryptic species in the wild is challenging without genetic confirmation. Morphological similarity complicates field studies.

How do environmental conditions influence cyst ornamentation and structure?

Salinity can alter process length, but effects vary within populations, suggesting internal genetic controls rather than uniform environmental impact. This variability complicates functional assumptions about ornamentation.

Can cyst morphology provide clues about evolutionary relationships?

Yes, fossil cyst morphology, when combined with genetics of living equivalents, supports phylogenetic reconstructions, showing good agreement with evolutionary patterns derived from living dinoflagellates. I think the close morphological similarity between living cysts and ancient "acritarchs" raises important questions for current research [17].

Are cysts indicators of harmful species?

Alexandrium cysts are notable, but morphology doesn't reliably indicate toxicity. Some toxic species may not form cysts, and others like *Pyrodinium* or *Lingulodinium* show variable toxicity, cautioning against generalizations.

Why are open-ocean cyst dynamics a research gap?

We lack knowledge about how cyst species of *Impagidinium* complete life cycles in deep water. Unclear sinking/floatation mechanisms and survival under extreme conditions highlight the need for sediment trap and molecular studies.

Applications, Implications, and Advice

How have cyst records contributed to understanding past climate change?

Cyst species tied to temperature-defined biogeographic zones serve as warm/cold climate indicators. Anne de Vernal's North Atlantic studies use cysts for paleoceanographic modeling, though sediment transport limits precise sea surface temperature (SST) reconstructions. I prefer the term "environmental signals" over quantitative proxies at this stage of understanding. I summarized cyst signals in Dale, 1996 [11].

Can cyst assemblages indicate past ocean productivity?

Yes, cysts of heterotrophic species dominate major upwelling/high nutrient zones now, signaling high productivity. Cysts of the more mixotrophic cosmopolitan *Lingulodinium* or *Protoceratium* dominate relaxation phases of upwelling off the California Coast and off large river plumes off Angola. These signals are also documented from older cored sediments.

What are significant climate reconstructions from cyst studies?

Examples include *Gymnodinium nolleri* appearing in the Skagerrak during the Medieval Warm Period (2,000 years ago) and receding in the Little Ice Age [12]. Karen Zonneveld described climate during Roman times in the Mediterranean. *Pyrodinium bahamense* records show global expansions during warming periods. Both warm and cold-water indicator species are identified from present-day cyst distributions, allowing their application as fossils for use in climate reconstructions from marine sediments analogous with fossil pollen in terrestrial studies.

How reliable are cyst-based reconstructions compared to other paleo-indicators?

Early transfer function models were statistically and ecologically challenged, especially for deep sea cyst records of predominantly coastal species. Coastal settings allow reliable signals if environmental conditions are stable, but

transport of the lighter cysts in open oceans complicates comparisons with foraminifera and other mineralized microfossils commonly used. However, the latter are subject to dissolution, especially at high latitudes whereas organic-walled cysts remain recoverable using palynology methods. This has increased the value of cysts as paleo-indicators in paleoceanography and deep geological applications. The use of best analogues from a global database is now preferred as a basis for cyst-based reconstructions, but the analogues still rely on the same assumed relationship between cysts and surface waters. The precision of reconstructions of actual sea surface temperatures and salinities using cyst proxies may still be challenged.

How do cysts inform past harmful algal blooms?

Cysts identify HAB species in sediments post-bloom, aiding “after-the fact” species identification in understudied regions. However, geological “bloom” evidence is often misinterpreted, as species dominance may reflect regular abundance, not a bloom event. Blooms cannot be unequivocally identified in the geological record.

Do cyst distribution patterns suggest climate-driven population shifts?

Yes, *Gymnodinium nolleri* and *Pyrodinium bahamense* records show climate-linked expansions and retreats, correlating with warming/cooling periods such as the Medieval Warm Period and Little Ice Age [12].

Can modern cyst deposition patterns predict future climate-driven changes?

Cyst records provide historical climate insights, suggesting future trends, but bloom prediction remains unreliable due to complex water-column dynamics. Past and present data together can provide important risk assessments for considering possible future climate-driven change.

How have human activities like eutrophication influenced cyst assemblages?

In the nutrient restricted Oslo Fjord, eutrophication doubled the amount of nutrients, and doubled the amounts of

Fig. 5. Barrie at home, 2019.

cysts, largely by providing extra nutrients to late-blooming *Lingulodinium* previously restricted to nutrients remaining after spring and summer depletion [14–16]. Industrial pollution reduced cyst numbers in another fjord, presumably due to adverse effects on phytoplankton. Eutrophication effects in another more polluted Japanese bay were associated with a shift towards heterotroph species, comparable to the natural upwelling signal. Studies investigating human impact should target sites to isolate one type of impact if possible – e.g. eutrophication with little or no industrial effects (clean-up efforts, as in Oslo Fjord, reverse these signals, offering encouraging feedback for environmental management).

How useful are cysts for ballast water monitoring and invasive species detection?

Cysts are critical for detecting invasive HAB species in ballast tanks, with proven success in identifying global transfer vectors. Regular sediment surveys enhance monitoring efforts. Comparisons between cysts in shipping harbor sediments and nearby unaffected zones help identify invasives, and cysts in well dated sediment cores help trace new introductions.

Can cyst DNA analysis improve HAB species detection?

Yes, DNA analysis distinguishes morphologically similar species such as in *Alexandrium*. Field-friendly kits could improve monitoring, but differentiating cyst-specific DNA from motile DNA in sediments is a challenge – we need confidence that motile DNA degenerates

rapidly if DNA is used for quantifying seed banks.

What are the most promising new techniques for studying cysts?

Single-cyst molecular analysis, genetic barcoding, and AI-driven identification offer improved precision and scalability for cyst research.

Are there cyst-based bio-indicators for water quality or ecosystem health?

Cysts show potential as water quality indicators, like EU benthic foraminifera standards. Cyst surveys for aquaculture site licensing and monitoring can detect toxic cysts and eutrophication effects.

How can AI or machine learning contribute to cyst identification?

AI, as demonstrated by Robert Williams [10], enables automated cyst identification and remote slide sharing among experts, mirroring pathology practices. This could revolutionize global cyst research collaboration.

What open questions remain about cysts in ecosystem resilience?

Most questions remain open, as cysts are one life stage of one group. Their ecosystem impact is limited but potentially significant, requiring humble acknowledgment of broader biological complexities.

How can cyst studies be integrated into global monitoring efforts?

Cyst surveys provide multi-year data from each sediment sample, complementing plankton sampling requiring many per year. This potentially adds monitoring possibilities for tracing global cyst-forming HAB species in sediment surveys investigating global change (chemical pollution, microplastic etc.). The cysts would also provide signals for other possible environmental changes if surveys continued for long-term monitoring. DNA-based monitoring should be standardized for aquaculture and environmental management.

What advice would you give early-career cyst researchers?

Explore dinoflagellates beyond HAB species or any other speciality, appreciating their diverse ecologic strategies.

HAB species are singled out primarily for their threat to humans – we need to know more about blooms as a phenomenon of phytoplankton generally to better understand HABs. Consider the history of geo-bio cyst research and value interdisciplinary connections. Remember we are paid to think. Resist funding pressures that stifle independent thought, share findings openly, and avoid exaggerating HAB impacts. Read enough to avoid “reinventing the wheel”. Commit to helping others to enter the field as you were helped and contribute to the good fellowship that fosters productive science. Enjoy the privileges a part in scientific endeavors brings.

If restarting your career, what aspect of cyst research would you focus on?

I'd delve into dinoflagellate phylogeny, exploring their possible evolutionary role between prokaryotes and eukaryotes, using cysts and protist biology as evidence. I think the close detailed morphological similarities between some ancient acritarchs and living cysts suggests a much longer geological history for the group, more in line with geochemical markers and molecular phylogenies than the current paleontological mantra [17].

How can cyst research support aquaculture?

Cyst surveys during aquaculture site licensing can detect toxic species, preventing HAB risks. Ongoing sediment monitoring tracks eutrophication-induced cyst beds, ensuring sustainable fish farming practices.

How do cysts compare to other microfossils as climate proxies?

Unlike foraminifera, cysts resist dissolution in northern oceans, making them valuable for paleoceanography. However, sediment transport complicates deep sea reconstructions based on the assumption that cysts on the seabed reflect conditions in directly lying surface waters.

Why is skepticism warranted for geological HAB evidence?

Fossil cyst dominance may reflect regular abundance in populations, not blooms. Environmental factors like droughts or gas leaks often explain mass mortality, not toxicity, urging cautious interpretation of past HABs.

How can researchers avoid exaggerating HAB importance?

Acknowledge that HABs are well-monitored in many badly affected regions,

posing less risk than many other health threats. Science has a responsibility to inform the public of state-of-the-art knowledge, for example stating the difference between known dangerously toxic species and those with traces of a chemical “poison” not known to adversely affect humans.

Barrie Dale, University of Oslo
barrie.dale@geo.uio.no

References

1. Evitt W R 1963. *PNAS* 49(2):158–164, 298–302.
2. Wall D & Dale B 1966. *Nature* 211(5053):1025–1026.
3. Wall et al. 1967. *Phycologia* 6:83–86.
4. Wall D & Dale B 1968. *Micropaleontology* 14(3):265–304.
5. Dale B 1976. *Rev Paleobot Palynol* 22:39–60.
6. Wall D et al. 1977. *Mar Micropal* 2:121–200.
7. Dale B 1977. *Sarsia* 63(1):29–34.
8. Dale et al 1978. *Science* 201:1223–1225.
9. Dale et al 2005. *Recent developments in Applied Biostratigraphy*. In: Powell AJ & Riding JB (Eds) *The Micropalaeontological Society, Special Publications*. pp. 179–203.
10. García-Moreiras et al 2025. *Mar Micropaleontol* 102502.
11. Dale B. 1996. In: Jansonius J, McGregor DC, editors. *Palynology: Principles and applications* 3. Dallas, Texas: American Association of Stratigraphic Palynologists Foundation; p. 1249–1275.
12. Dale B et al. 1993. T.J. Smayda, Y. Shimizu (Eds.), *Toxic Phytoplankton Blooms in the Sea*, Elsevier, Amsterdam (1993), pp. 47–52. [Note from Editor: In this paper, the authors use the name *G. catenatum* for another species that is now recognised as *Gymnodinium nolleri*].
13. Dale B 1983. In: Fryxel GA (Ed). *Survival strategies of the algae*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (UK), pp. 69–136.
14. Dale B 2000. In: Martin RE (Eds), *Environmental Micropaleontology. Topics in Geobiology* 15:305–321. Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-4167-7_14
15. Dale B 2009. *J Sea Res* 61(1–2):103–113.
16. Dale B 2001. In: Gili JM et al (Eds), *A marine science odyssey into the 21st Century*; *Sci Mar* 65(Suppl. 2):257–272.
17. Dale B 2022. *Mar Sci Eng* 11(3):533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11030533>.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17220281>

Fig. 6. Grandad Barrie with his grandson Harald on home ground, 2024.

Youssef Halim, the Creator of a “Celebrity”: *Alexandrium*

If the history of planktology were to be written, the dinoflagellate genus *Alexandrium* would require a special chapter. That chapter would be dedicated to *Alexandrium*'s taxonomic back-and-forths, all the more significant because some of its species are the main producers of paralyzing shellfish toxins (PSTs). The chapter began in the later decades of the 20th century with descriptions of some species and continues today actively in the field of molecular biology. The story involves years of lively taxonomic discussions between specialists and, in particular, the relationship between two renowned researchers, Prof. Youssef Halim and Prof. Enrique Balech, which will be explored in this essay. The link established between these two scientists constitutes a rich nodal point, and it will be addressed here mainly through an analysis of scientific publications but also by drawing on personal experiences, including my own.

The expression “mainly” is used due to the fact that, unfortunately, after Prof. Balech's death, all the documentation in his folders disappeared – not only original drawings and descriptions and his copious correspondence, but also an old bibliography of reprints and books obtained after laborious efforts made throughout his life. Envelopes addressed to: “E. Balech, C.C. 64, 7630-Necochea, Argentina”—how much correspondence, sometimes including plankton samples from all over the world, was received! Some people may not know what “C.C.” means: *Casilla de Correo* in Spanish (P.O. Box, Post Office Box in English). In today's digital world we deal with e-mail folders, which correspond in part to the old C.C.– wooden or metal boxes in masonry post offices. And we wonder how many letters from Y. Halim would have reached that C.C.– because the correspondence between Youssef and Enrique must have been very interesting, without doubt!

Dinoflagellates were once considered as microalgae by some researchers and as zooflagellates by others.

Certainly, some phylogenetic groups possess photosynthetic pigments and therefore are autotrophs, while others lack plastids and feed by predation or other mechanisms. This is why some taxonomists applied the rules of the International Code of Botanical Nomenclature (ICBN, today International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants; [1]), while others applied the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). These positions are hardly debated nowadays, and this advance is due in part to the great ideas presented by Lynn Margulis about the process of successive incorporation and integration of organelles such as mitochondria and chloroplasts as endosymbionts [2]. These ideas are linked with an immense body of phylogenetic research that allows us today to understand the relationships of the major groups of life on Earth. Balech, aware of these aspects and maintaining a broad outlook, generally adhered in his works to the provisions of the ICZN. It is possible that Halim did as well, since in his original publication of *Alexandrium minutum* ([3]; see Fig. 1)-as well as in that of *Gessnerium mochimaensis* ([4])—he did not include a brief Latin description that, until 2011, was required the famous Art. 39 of the ICBN to validate the description of a new species [1]. However, perhaps wishing that his new genus *Gessnerium* would be considered validly described, Halim added a short Latin description for the latter two years later [5].

By the time he described *Alexandrium*, Halim had obtained his PhD from the University of Paris (1956), pursuing research on dinoflagellate ecology at the Station Zoologique of Villefranche-sur-Mer [6]. Based on that experience, he was able to recognize that he was facing a taxonomic novelty while studying material collected in the port of Alexandria during a spectacular bloom. There, although without records of marine fauna mortality, *A. minutum* caused a *phénomène dit des 'eaux rouges*—i.e.:

red tide—that reached 26 million cells per liter [3].

The story that culminates with *Alexandrium* begins with the old genus *Gonyaulax* Diesing, within which a group of species was recognized as the “*tamarensis* group” or “*Gonyaulax tamarensis* complex”, sometimes also called the “*catenella* group.” Several morphological characters – such as the number and position of thecal plates and the lack of horns, spines and thecal ornamentation – set them apart from *Gonyaulax*. *G. tamarensis* was described by the English planktologist Mary Lebour in 1925, the first species published as belonging to this group. Later, other genera and species of *Gonyaulax* (e.g. *G. catenella*, a worldwide distributed PST producer), as well as infraspecific taxa related to the *G. tamarensis* complex, were described or proposed. Within this panorama, it was noticed that Paulsen in 1904 and under another genus, had described *Goniodoma ostenfeldii*, a species that should also be considered within the “*tamarensis* group” [7]. Importantly, Karen Steidinger was the first to suggest that this species complex deserved another genus and noted that *A. minutum* Halim was part of this group [8]. These taxonomic observations were simultaneously discussed by Balech in a study of microplankton communities from the tropical Atlantic Ocean [9].

During the 1970s this idea matured, and in the 1980s it became a point of great interest and dissent among specialists, since it was proposed either to adopt new generic names or to reuse existing ones. Researchers such as Loeblich and Loeblich [10] suggested the name *Gessnerium* for the “*tamarensis* group of *Gonyaulax*”, but other specialists considered that this group should have been divided into two genera –*Alexandrium*, and a new created genus, *Protogonyaulax*– depending on the type of contact between the first apical plate and the apical pore plate [11].

This issue was settled at the Fourth International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton held in Lund, Sweden, in 1989, during a meeting specially convened to make a decision. As stated there, it was time for consensus because it was confusing to chemists, biologists, and the public alike to use so many names. In the workshop held in Lund, following lively discussion, the

genera *Gonyaulax*, *Protogonyaulax* and *Gessnerium* were set aside, and the use of the name *Alexandrium* was definitively established [12]. The objective of consensus, proposed by participants such as Y. Fukuyo, G. Hallegraeff, B. Dale and F.J.R. Taylor, in addition to E. Balech, K.A. Steidinger and O. Moestrup, together toxin chemists like the also distinguished Y. Shimizu—was reached!

The study and interpretation of the plate pattern, following the nomenclature of the Kofoidian system with some corrections in thecal tabulation, allowed Balech to put the group in a single genus and to adopt the name *Alexandrium* Halim, the first generic name available and validly published for a species of the “*tamarensis* group.” By showing that the type of contact between the first apical plate and the apical pore plate may vary within the same species – e.g. in *A. fraterculus* and *A. kutnerae* as well as in the type species to an even greater degree – Balech [13] provided a good foundation for the genus *Alexandrium*. Thus, *A. minutum* was designed as the type species and the harbour of Alexandria its type locality. In doing this, he had to redefine *Alexandrium* and its type species, *A. minutum* [13–15]. An important aspect was that the sample upon which he made his study not only came from the type locality but also that the species identification had been checked by Halim himself. As a final milestone, Balech published a book that summarized the taxonomic and historical information on the knowledge of all these taxa, a product of many years of studies based on samples from cultures and plankton samples from more than 16 countries from all around the world [16].

There is no doubt that it was during the years when Enrique was writing his book on *Alexandrium* that he was in contact with Youssef. How interesting it would have been to explore that correspondence! A small clue is found in Enrique’s book on *Alexandrium* where he acknowledges that Youssef sent him a red tide sample from the Bay of Alexandria. Enrique must have received this well before 1989, because already at the Lund Conference of the same year, he published the emended diagnosis of *Alexandrium* for the “*tamarensis* group” [12, 15].

An example of what these different taxonomic and nomenclatural criteria

meant in Argentina during that period is the names given to a species that produced the first PST outbreak. Initially it was identified as *Gonyaulax excavata* [17] and later identified as *Alexandrium tamarensis* [18]. Recently, however, and following ribosomal phylogenetic studies, it has been recognized as *Alexandrium catenella* [19]. The paralyzing shellfish poisoning outbreak caused in its first bloom was recorded in a restricted area of a frontal Patagonian system, where sexual forms and resting cysts in sediments were observed. From that initial outbreak, the toxic area expanded through successive stages to cover nearly all the Argentine sea suggesting that the expansion of the toxicity area followed a stepwise pattern with the formation of dispersal centers associated to frontal systems [17, 20]. In my country, Argentina, and almost 20 years before this PST-producing species was detected, another member of the “*tamarensis* group” was described. Indeed, shortly after Youssef published *A. minutum*, Enrique described *Gonyaulax fraterculus* (now *Alexandrium fraterculus*) from plankton samples collected near the coast of Mar del Plata [21]. Today, other species of *Alexandrium* are also known in the Southwest Atlantic region, this time with the addition of molecular analysis of ribotype groups to microscopic morphological studies [22].

Finally, let us take a panoramic look at this topic by consulting a pair of worldwide databases which represent the result and constant contributions made by many colleagues specialized in the study of marine biota.

AlgaeBase, a database of information on algae, currently, in 2020, lists 33 species for the genus *Alexandrium*, some of them dedicated to distinguished planktonologists—e.g. *Alexandrium balechii* (Steidinger) Balech, *Alexandrium margalefii* Balech—and all of them as entities currently accepted taxonomically [23]. Regarding the type species of the genus *Alexandrium*, an important volume of information is presented for *A. minutum* Halim in this database with references to synonymy, associated toxins, worldwide distribution and numerous bibliographical citations.

The online database maintained by the IOC Harmful Algal Bloom Program and the World Register of Marine Spe-

cies presents in its catalogue of the world’s toxic or harmful microalgal species an updated list that includes 17 *Alexandrium* species in the Gonyaulacales order [24]. I should add that these issues continue to be debated. An example is the proposal by Gómez and Artigas [25]¹ to split *Alexandrium* and reinstate some of the previously mentioned genera. The following year, a response from fifty specialists [26] argued that “Morphological and phylogenetic data do not support the split of *Alexandrium* into four genera,” and suggested that chemotaxonomy and cyst morphology should be taken into account for an integrative taxonomy.

Postscript

One of the reasons that led me to write the preceding paragraphs is the clear memory of a day in 1996 when we suddenly received a visit from Enrique Balech in our laboratory in Mar del Plata. With a pride he could not conceal despite his reserved nature, he gave us a copy of his recently published book on *Alexandrium*. I vividly remember the sympathy and recognition that he expressed on that occasion for his Egyptian colleague Youssef Halim.

Another reason, my dear reader, and with your permission to express it because this time it is of a personal nature, is the appreciation that I have maintained in my memory for Prof. Youssef Halim. The first time I met him personally was at the 14th International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms held in Crete, Greece, in 2010. After the conference we wished to visit Cairo and, being there, we were able to appreciate Youssef as a true gentleman, when he advised and guided us in the best way.

Acknowledgements

I thank Karen Steidinger, Elena Fabro, Hala Halim and Rubén M. Negri for providing some bibliographic articles because, after my retirement and two years ago, I donated my library.

References

1. Turland NJ et al 2018. Eds. *International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi,*

¹) Updated by editor-in-chief

and plants (Shenzhen Code) adopted by the Nineteenth International Botanical Congress Shenzhen, China, July 2017. *Regnum Vegetabile* 159. Glashütten: Koeltz Botanical Books. DOI <https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>

2. Graham LE & Wilcox LW 2000. *Algae*. Prentice-Hall, 640 pp.
3. Halim Y 1960. *Vie et Milieu* 11(1):102–105.
4. Halim Y 1967. *Int Revue ges Hydrobiol* 52:701–755.
5. Halim Y 1969. *Int Revue ges Hydrobiol* 54:619.
6. Halim Y 1960. *Ann Inst Oceanogr* 38(2):124–232.
7. Balech E & Tangen K 1985. *Sarsia* 70(4):333–343.
8. Steidinger KA 1971. *Phycologia* 10:183–187.
9. Balech E 1971. *Microplancton del Atlántico Ecuatorial Oeste (Equalant I)*. Servicio de Hidrografía Naval, Buenos Aires, H 654, 103 pp, 12 pl.
10. Loeblich AR III & Loeblich LA 1979. In: *Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms*. Taylor & Seliger (Eds), Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 41–46.
11. Taylor FJR 1979. In: *Toxic Dinoflagellate*

12. Steidinger KA & Moestrup Ø 1990. Workshop. In: *Toxic Marine Phytoplankton*. Granéli et al (Eds.), Elsevier Science Publishing Co, Inc. pp. 522–523.
13. Balech E 1989. *Phycologia*, 28(2):206–211.
14. Balech E 1985. In: *Toxic Dinoflagellates*. Anderson et al (Eds), Elsevier Science Publishing Co, Inc pp. 33–38.
15. Balech E 1990. In: *Toxic Marine Phytoplankton*. Granéli E et al (Eds.). Elsevier Science Publishing Co., Inc. p. 77.
16. Balech E 1995. *The Genus Alexandrium Halim (Dinoflagellata)*. Sherkin Island Marine Station, Sherkin Island, Co. Cork, Ireland. 151 pp.
17. Carreto JI et al 1985. In: *Toxic Dinoflagellates*. Anderson DM et al (Eds). Elsevier Sci Publ Co, NY, pp. 147–152.
18. Carreto JI et al 1998. In: *Harmful Algae*. Reguera et al (Eds), Xunta de Galicia and IOC of UNESCO, pp. 131–134.
19. Krock B et al 2018. *Oceanography* 31 (4), <https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2018.403>.
20. Akselman R et al 2008. In: *Harmful Algae*. Moestrup et al (Eds.) Proceedings

- of the 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae. International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae and IOC of UNESCO, Copenhagen. pp. 243–245.
21. Balech E 1964. *Bol Inst Biol Mar, Mar del Plata* 4:1–49.
22. Fabro E et al 2017. *J Phycol* 53:1206–1222, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpy.12574>.
23. Guiry MD & Guiry GM 2020. *AlgaeBase*. World-wide electronic publication, National University of Ireland, Galway. <http://www.algaebase.org>.
24. Lundholm N et al (Eds) (2009 onwards). *IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Micro Algae*. Accessed at <https://www.marinespecies.org/hab> on 2025-09-02. doi:10.14284/362
25. Gómez F & Artigas L. 2019. *J Mar Biol* 17 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1284104>.
26. Mertens KN et al 2020. *Harmful Algae* 98:101902.

Author

Rut Akselman, Researcher (retired), INIDEP, Mar del Plata, Argentina

Fig. 1. — a à d, *Alexandrium minutum* nov. g., nov. sp., différents spécimens en vue ventrale. — e, vue dorsale de l'épithèque. — f, vue apicale de l'épithèque. — g, vue antapicale de l'hypothèque. — h, les plaques sulcales; sp. : sulcale postérieure; v.m.d. : ventrale médiane droite; v.m.g. : ventrale médiane gauche; v.a. : ventrale antérieure; v. ac. : ventrale accessoire; lg : première plaque cingulaire. — j, les sept plaques cingulaires. (a et e x 1635, b x 1580, c et d x 1405, f x 1725, g x 1575).

Fig. 1. Front cover of the journal *Vie et Milieu* (1960, Volume XI, Fasc. 1) and original drawings in Fig. 1 (legend below) of *Alexandrium minutum* nov. g., nov. sp. published by Y. Halim.

Rut Akselman's essay was originally solicited by Hala Halim and Makram Gerges for a planned memorial volume for Youssef Halim that they are co-editing. Per the author's wishes, her colleague Vivian A. Lutz was apprised of further editorial revisions made posthumously to this essay.

Rut Akselman In Memoriam

Rut Akselman Cardella (June 1948 – July 2025) earned her PhD in Biological Sciences from the University of Buenos Aires in 1996 [1]. Rut worked for over 40 years as a researcher at the Fisheries Research Institute (INIDEP = Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero). In the INIDEP she was part of the group (with José Carreto, Ruben Negri and Hugo Benavides) which carried out pioneering studies in the 1980's about *Alexandrium catenella* (as *Gonyaulax excavata/tamarensis*), the causative agent of severe Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) outbreaks in the Southern Cone of South America [2]. Results from these studies advanced knowledge on the dynamics of *Alexandrium* blooms, initiated in frontal areas off Peninsula Valdés (Argentine Patagonia), their impact in the food web and the key role of mixotrophic dinoflagellates, such as *Polykrikos* species, in the bloom decay [3–4].

Rut devoted her professional life to studies related to the ecology and taxonomy of marine dinoflagellates, in particular those responsible for toxic algal blooms in South America, such as

Rut Akselman

Alexandrium catenella, *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Protoceratium reticulatum*, *Azadinium luciferelloides* and other *Azadinium* species [1–13, 20]. A passionate and meticulous microalgal taxonomist, Rut made a great contribution to editorial activities related to this topic, first as Associate Editor of the INIDEP journal (Marine and Fishery Sciences, MAFIS) and later as a member of the IOC-UNESCO Task Team on Algal Taxonomy. She (co-)described, amongst others, *Protoperidinium balechii* [14; as

Peridinium], *Gymnodinium bonaerense* [16], *Lebouraia pusilla* [18; as *Diplopetta*], *Scrippsiella patagonica* [19] and *Azadinium luciferelloides* [20]. She also took an interest in resting cysts [21].

Rut was also a plastic artist who used her own art exhibitions to show the beauty of microalgal shapes to the public (Figs. 2–3, [22]). Every Christmas season, Rut's friends and colleagues were presented with a calendar illustrated with photos of her creative embroidery and collages reproducing her favourite dinoflagellates species.

We will always remember her gentle nature, her sweet and luminous gaze, her professional dedication, her endless capacity for wonder, as well as her adoration and respect for her teachers who motivated her, particularly Professor Enrique Balech, who significantly marked her career.

In her quest to preserve E. Balech's legacy, Rut Akselman digitized all of his publications, making them available to the international scientific community through the IOC-HAB website and the FANSA and ANCA groups of HAB experts [23]. She also served the HAB commu-

Fig. 1. Rut Akselman (with Monica Lion) during her stay in the IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre in Vigo to work with the IOC-HAEDAT database. Vigo, Spain October 2006.

Fig. 2. Rut Akselman during her last art exhibition "Textile Art of Argentine Dinoflagellates" held in Mar de Plata, Argentina, August 2017 [22].

nity with many hours of dedication to update information on HAB events for the IOC-HAEDAT database [2].

Rut Akselman passed away from pancreatic cancer on July 21, 2025, in Mar del Plata, surrounded by her family. Shortly before her passing, one of Rut's concerns was the publication of the note on *Alexandrium* she had written for a volume dedicated to Prof. Youssef Halim. Coinciding with the tenth anniversary of Prof Halim's passing, Hala Halim and Makram Gerges kindly allowed the posthumous publication of Rut's essay in the Red Tides Archives section of Harmful Algae News, in homage to Rut and Prof Halim.

Rest in peace, dear friend.

Selected publications of Rut Akselman

1. Akselman R 1996. *Estudios ecológicos en el Golfo San Jorge y adyacencias (Atlántico Sudoccidental): Distribución, abundancia y variación estacional del fitoplancton en relación a factores Físico-químicos y la dinámica hidrológica*. PhD Thesis, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales. Universidad de Buenos Aires.
2. Akselman R et al 2008. In Moestrup Ø et al (eds). *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae.*, Copenhagen, Denmark, September 4–8, 2006. Pp. 243–245

3. Carreto JI et al 1985. In Anderson D et al. (Eds). *Toxic dinoflagellates*. Elsevier Sci Publ Co, NY, pp. 47–152
4. Carreto JI et al 1993. *Presencia de veneno paralizante de moluscos en hígado de caballa de la región costera bonaerense*. *Publicaciones INIDEP Doc científico* 2:53–59.
5. Akselman R & Santinelli N 1989. *Physis (Buenos Aires) A* 47(112):43–44.
6. Akselman R 1994. *Especies fitoplanctónicas toxigénicas o potencialmente nocivas detectadas en el Mar Argentino*. *IOC Workshop Report N° 10:2–4*
7. Montoya et al. 1997. *Rev Invest Desarr Pesq* 11 :145–152. <http://hdl.handle.net/1834/1939>
8. Akselman R et al 1998. In Reguera B et al (eds.) *Harmful Algae*. Xunta de Galicia and IOC of UNESCO, Santiago de Compostela. pp. 122–123.
9. Akselman R & Negri RM 2012. *Harmful Algae* 19:30–38. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2012.05.004.
10. Mendez SM et al 2012. In Pagou CR & Hallegraeff G. (eds). *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Harmful Algae*. International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae and IOC of UNESCO. pp. 134–136.
11. Akselman R et al 2014. *Revista de Biología Marina y Oceanografía* 49:511–526. doi.org/10.4067/S0718-19572014000300008.
12. Akselman et al 2015. *Harmful Algae* 45:40–52. doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2015.03.001.
13. Krock B et al 2018. *Oceanography* 31(4). doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2018.403
14. Akselman R 1972. *Darwiniana* 17:384–392.
15. Balech E et al 1984. *Rev Invest Desarr Pesq* 4:5–20.
16. Akselman R 1985. *Serie: Physis, Secc A*. 43 (104):39–50.
17. Akselman R 1986. *Serie: Darwiniana*. 27(1–4):9–17.
18. Balech E & Akselman R 1988. *Physis (Buenos Aires) A* 46(110):27–30.
19. Akselman R & Keupp H 1990. *Mar Micropaleontol* 16:169–179.
20. Tillmann U & Akselman R 2016. *Phycol Res* 64:160–175. doi.org/10.1111/pre.12133.
21. Akselman R 1987. *Quistes planctónicos de dinofíceas en áreas de plataforma del Atlántico sudoccidental*. I. Reporte taxonómico de la Familia Peridiniaceae Ehrenberg. *Bolm Inst oceanogr S Paulo* 35(1):17–32.
22. *Dinoflagelados de Argentina Arte Textil - Rut Akselman-Cardella 2017*. <https://www.facebook.com/media/set/?set=a.1556369857758805.1073741887.343210979074705&type=3>
23. HARP: Publications (1944-2008) of Professor Enrique Balech. <https://goosocean.org/document-list/135>

Authors

Silvia Méndez, Almería 4536, Montevideo 11400, Uruguay

Beatriz Reguera, IEO-CSIC, Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo, Spain

Email corresponding authors:
silviamedez52@gmail.com
beatriz.reguera@ieo.csic.es

Fig. 3. Rut's artistic view of polymorphism among *Azadinium* species [22].

Carved Wooden Models of Microalgae

I have observed many types of microalgae, particularly unarmored dinoflagellates, using both a light microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM). The SEM, with its deep depth of field, allows me to capture three-dimensional images of microalgae, making it an essential reference for my wood-carved models.

The idea of creating carved wooden models of microalgae first came to me when I was trying to explain the paths of the sulcus and cingulum of *Warnowia* sp. to a university professor. The *Warnowia* sp. I was discussing had a cingulum that encircled the cell more than three times, with a sulcus running parallel to it. However, using only light microscope photographs, I was unable to fully convince him. His quiet remark, "Are you sure?" stayed in my mind.

At that moment, I realized that instead of relying on flat images like photographs, I could create a three-dimensional model to explain the structure more effectively. Up until then, I had

been enjoying woodcraft as a hobby, creating small decorative carvings on wooden boxes, so I decided to try carving a wooden model.

At that time, however, my wood-working skills were still undeveloped, and I was not able to create the *Warnowia* sp. model right away. It took several years to complete, and by then, the professor had already gained a thorough understanding of *Warnowia*'s morphology. I never had the opportunity to explain it again, and I doubt he remembers the conversation. However, that experience was what led me to start carving wooden models of microalgae.

Even now, I do not consider myself a sculptor. My goal is not to create works of art but to reproduce microalgae as accurately as possible within my own capabilities. In woodcarving, however, there are times when I make mistakes by shaving off too much material, beyond the point of recovery. Because of this, I once tried making models with clay. Clay modeling is very useful, but it

requires its own set of skills, and I felt that acquiring them would take time. In the end, I decided to continue making models with wood, a medium I was already familiar with.

The process of making wood carvings of microalgae varies depending on the shape of each species. In this case, I will describe the production process using *Chattonella marina* var. *antiqua* and *Alexandrium tamarensense* as examples. In general, wood is softer and easier to carve when it retains some moisture, but as it dries, it often warps or cracks. For this reason, well-dried wood is typically used for carving.

Making *Alexandrium tamarensense*

I wanted to create a model of a two-cell colony. The material I used was a square cypress prism (Fig. 1). Since this species has a nearly circular cross-section, I shaped the square prism into a cylinder using a wood lathe (Fig. 2). Keeping in mind the widest part of the cin-

Figures 1–7. Steps (1 to 7) in the creation of a microalgal model of *Alexandrium tamarensense*. (lower right corner).

Figures 8–14. Steps (8 to 14) in the creation of a microalgal model of *Chattonella marina* (lower right corner).

gulum, I carved the material further to form the rough shape of two connected cells (Fig. 3). From that stage onwards, it seemed more practical to work on them separately, so I cut the piece in half with a saw (Fig. 4). I then refined the shape further, gradually bringing it closer to the final form. I used various tools, including chisels, hatchets, carving knives, and routers. For fine details, I used carving knives, a micro-router, and sandpaper to refine the shape (Fig. 5). Finally, I connected the two cells and mounted the model on a base, completing the wood carving process (Figs. 6–7). Since I wanted to represent the thecal plates within the sulcus and cingulum in this model, I decided not to attach flagella.

Making *Chattonella marina* var. *antiqua*

This species has a slightly flattened cell shape, so I used thick cypress board.

I first outlined *C. marina* var. *antiqua* on the material (Fig. 8). The original drawing I referred to was one I made when this species caused a red tide in Hiroshima Bay for the first time in 1969. I then roughly cut it out along the outline using a saw (Fig. 9). The rough shape was made with a hatchet (Fig. 10), and once that was complete, I refined it further using carving knives and a router (Figs. 11–12).

At this stage, I could have considered the model complete, but *C. marina* var. *antiqua* has many small granules on its cell surface, which appear to be oil droplets. I wanted to represent these in the model.

To do this, I marked the positions of the granules using a hole punch (Fig. 13) and then carved around them with a micro-router to make them stand out. I further polished the surface with sandpaper (Fig. 14). This was a labour-intensive process.

Chattonella has two flagella: a swimming flagellum and a trailing flagellum.

I made the flagella using rattan. Finally, I mounted the model on a base, completing the carving process.

Varnishing

Next, I applied varnish. Regular varnish is meant to coat the surface of the wood, but the one I use penetrates the material and hardens it, strengthening the wood structure. As I grow older, I find it increasingly difficult to carve hard wood, so recently I have been focusing on using softer materials for carving and reinforcing them with varnish. This process has now become essential. Finally, I applied varnish to both *A. tamarense* and *C. marina* var. *antiqua*, completing the models.

Author

Haruyoshi Takayama, Hatami, Ondo-cho, Kure, Hiroshima 737-1207, Japan

Email corresponding author:
T_haru4576@ybb.ne.jp

ISSHA Corner

Call for ICHA 2029 bids still open –

In the last Harmful Algae News issue we announced the opening of the call for bids for organizing the 23rd International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) in 2029. This call is still open.

The ICHA conferences are known for their high quality, vibrant interactions and great fun. They are supported by an extensive HAB community covering a range of HAB taxa and habitats, with excellent science ranging from the basics of HAB physiology, genetics, toxins and ecology to predictions and management of their risks.

Organizing an ICHA is a great opportunity to highlight HAB sciences in your region, bring together the international HAB community with local and regional stakeholders, and showcase HAB research from your region to the world. As ISSHA, we offer support in the organization of the scientific program, overall promotion, additional events (auction, workshops), and various travel support schemes.

The conference has a tradition of “continent-hopping” to reflect the global interest in HABs and to allow different regions to attract this periodic science inventory event to different regions. The conference being held in South America (Chile) in 2025 and Europe (Aberdeen, UK) in 2027, bids for 2029 from North America, Africa or the Australasian region would be particularly welcome.

Ideally, a bid is presented at the conference in Chile, but we are open to discuss a later date, where the bid can be presented to the ISSHA Council. Please contact the ISSHA President, Dedmer Van de Waal (d.vandewaal@nioo.knaw.nl), latest by **September 26** in case you are considering a bid, and/or if you have any questions.

From Proceedings to Special Issues

– For the upcoming 21st ICHA 2025 in Chile we will have a trial of coordinating special issues in different journals instead of conference proceedings. Currently, the call is out for contributions to the following special issues:

Harmful Algae and Microbes: From Molecules to Ecosystems, in Micro-

organisms (https://www.mdpi.com/journal/microorganisms/special_issues/7HRPDCDP58)

Advances in Planktonic Harmful Algae Research from Marine and Freshwater Environments, in Journal of Plankton Research <https://academic.oup.com/plankt/pages/call-for-papers>

At the gates of the next ICHA, at the end of the world: Punta Arenas, Chile

With just a few weeks to go before the next edition of ICHA, it is timely to highlight some of the most relevant aspects awaiting us in the city of Punta Arenas, Chile. Much dedication has gone into the planning and organisation, but as the start approaches, numerous and varied requests continue to arise, and the interest of colleagues sometimes exceeds the logistical capacity of those of us who have gladly taken on the organisation of this twenty-first ICHA.

The conference will follow the typical structure of scientific activities, but will also open doors for the local community, who will have the chance to learn about HABs and aquatic sciences—without in any way detracting from the scientific programme. We have organised seven plenary lectures, delivered by national and international researchers with extensive experience in HABs, covering topics that range from cyanobacteria to the future of HAB studies. The official inauguration will take place on Monday, 20 October, with the participation of the Regional Governor and the Mayor of Punta Arenas. In addition, eight workshops are planned. One will be held in the week of 13–17 October, focusing on qPCR studies applied to microalgae. During the conference week (20–24 October), workshops will cover

topics including early warning systems for HABs, GlobalHAB planning for the coming years, the use and management of multiple oceanographic instruments, emerging global toxins, sustainable development and HAB management, and even a game with ecological foundations. Oral presentations will take place across 31 parallel sessions grouped into 14 thematic areas, scheduled from Monday to Friday. Alongside these, 180 posters will be displayed over two days (Monday 20 and Thursday 23), and a total of 45 Ignite Talks (fast-format presentations) will be given on Monday afternoon. A key element of any conference is the opportunity to share with colleagues and friends. Several activities will continue the traditions of past ICHA meetings, such as the Icebreaker event for young researchers on 19 October. On 21 October, the Welcome Party will feature local folklore performances, offering a taste of Chilean culture. One of the most anticipated events, the ISSHA Auction, will take place on the evening of 23 October, raising funds to support young students and researchers in attending future conferences. All of these activities will be hosted at the Dreams del Estrecho Hotel. Participants will also have the opportunity to explore Punta Arenas and its surroundings, with various tours arranged, including details on itineraries, costs, and operators. The conference will conclude with a gala dinner on 24 October, with transportation provided from the Dreams Hotel to ASMAR Quincho, the venue for this memorable closing event. We sincerely thank all those who entrusted us with their work in its various forms (oral, poster, and Ignite Talk), thereby contributing to the most up-to-date knowledge in HAB research. Our gratitude also extends to those travelling thousands of kilometres to take part, to the companies supporting the organisation, and to the Local Organising Committee, who have worked tirelessly to create an ICHA we hope will be truly unforgettable.

A fraternal hug —we look forward to seeing you soon.

**Mixoplankton session at the AGU/
ASLO Ocean Sciences meeting in
Glasgow, Scotland, 22-27 February
2026**

Many HAB species, including haptophyte and dinoflagellate species in particular, do not fit easily into the traditional “phytoplankton” and “microzooplankton” categories. Rather, they are best considered to be “mixoplankton”. The latter term refers to organisms, primarily protists, that can both photosynthesize and ingest other organisms as food. This distinction is important because we need to understand the trophic links involving HABs if we are to be able to predict their occurrence and impact. During the week of 23 February 2026, the Ocean Sciences meeting jointly sponsored by the American Geophysical Union and the Association for the Sciences of Limnology and Oceanography, will host a special session, “New Paradigms, Diverse Approaches, and Advances in Understanding Mixoplankton”. Physiology, trophic links, and other aspects of mixoplankton biol-

ogy and ecology will be featured. Information about the meeting can be found here: <https://www.agu.org/ocean-sciences-meeting>.

Contact: George McManus, University of Connecticut, george.mcmanus@uconn.edu

Light (DIC microscopy, 400 x) micrograph of a field specimen of Dinophysis acuminata full of digestive vacuoles indicating recent feeding on his prey (Mesodinium ciliates). Photo courtesy of Laura Escalera.

See <https://www.marum.de/en/13th-international-conference-on-modern-and-fossil-dinoflagellates/dino-13-general-information.html>

Dino13

13th conference on modern and fossil dinoflagellates

5-10 July 2026

First Announcement – Save the Date

Hosted by Karin Zonneveld
University of Bremen
&
Francesca Sangiorgi
University of Utrecht
&
Organizing Committee

First announcement of the 16th Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS)

Date: September 6th- 11th 2026

Venue: 'University of Exeter', Southwest England

Hosted by: Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture
Science (Cefas)

The ICMSS Conference Returns! hosted for the first time in the United Kingdom at the world-famous University of Exeter ([University of Exeter](https://www.exeter.ac.uk))

We're thrilled to announce the 16th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS) — the premier global forum for advancing shellfish food safety

Theme: One Health - Join leading scientists, regulators, and industry experts from around the world to explore the **interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health** in the context of **shellfish safety**

What to expect:

- Cutting-edge **oral and poster presentations**
- Hands-on **workshops**, expert **panels**, and **training sessions**
- Vibrant **networking and social events**
- A chance to experience **Exeter** — a historic city in the heart of the UK's thriving shellfish region

Save the Date!

Stay tuned for details on **registration** and **abstract submissions** — coming soon!

Only two weeks before the 21st ICHA Conference in Punta Arenas, Chile.

The Scientific Programme is already available, and don't forget the ISSHA Auction. You are still on time to contribute. See Takayama's donations for the auction!!

Visit the ISSHA and the Conference websites for the latest news
<https://issha.org/>
<https://icha2025.org>

Editors-in-chief

Beatriz Reguera
Kenneth N. Mertens

IPHAB

Chair Philipp Hess
Vice-Chair Begoña Ben-Gigirey

Task Team Chairs

Taxonomy Nina Lundholm
Biotoxins Philip Hess
HAIS/GHSR Maarten De Rijcke
Early Warning Bengt Karlson
Fish Kills Allan Cembella
Ciguatera Marie-Yasmine Dechraoui-Bottein
Desalination Donald M. Anderson

IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB Clarissa Anderson
PICES HAB Section Pengbin Wang

IOC UNESCO Regional Groups

IOCARIBE ANCA Gustavo Arencibia
FANSA Ana Martínez-Goicoechea
HANA Amany Ismael
WESTPAC-HAB Mitsunori Iwataki

ICES Working Groups

ICES-IOC WGHABD Dave Clarke, Lars-Johan Naustvoll
ICES-IOC-IMO WGBOSV Cynthia McKenzie

Regional Editors

Atlantic Europe: Maud Lemoine
Mediterranean Sea: Adriana Zingone
India: K.B. Padmakumar
Western Pacific: Chu Pin Leaw and Kazumi Wakita
North Africa: Amany Ismael
North America: Patricia Tester and Cynthia McKenzie
Central America and Caribe: Ernesto Mancera
South America: Patricio Díaz and Luiz Mafra
South Pacific: Mireille Chinain and Lesley Rhodes

Compiled and edited by

Beatriz Reguera
Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo, IEO (CSIC)
Vigo, Spain
Email: beatriz.reguera@ieo.csic.es
and Kenneth Neil Mertens
Ifremer, COAST, Concarneau, France
Email: kenneth.mertens@ifremer.fr

Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have articles, ideas for article or suggestions for special issues, and we will gladly collaborate with you.

FAO Esther Garrido Gamarro

Email: Esther.GarridoGamarro@fao.org

IAEA Kristof Moeller

Email: Kr.Moeller@iaea.org

Project Coordinator

Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC Science and Communication
Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen
Tel.: +45 23 26 02 46
Email: h.enevoldsen@unesco.org

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17218768>

Deadline to submit material for next issue
15 November 2025

Disclaimer: The opinions expressed herein are those of the authors indicated and do not necessarily reflect the views of UNESCO or its IOC. Texts may be freely reproduced and translated (except when reproduction or translation rights are indicated as reserved), provided that mention is made of the author and source and a copy sent to the Editors.

**The publication of Harmful Algae News
is sponsored by the Department of Biology,
University of Copenhagen.**